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**Multi-scale numerical simulation of a
tsunami using mesh adaptive
methods**

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Abstract

Mesh adaptive methods are typically categorised as either *h-adaptive* or *r-adaptive*. In two dimensions, the former involves operations altering the number of mesh degrees of freedom by the insertion or deletion of element edges, while the latter hold both the number of degrees of freedom and the mesh topology fixed and redistribute mesh entities (vertices, edges and elements) geometrically. *Anisotropic mesh adaptivity* seeks to incorporate aspects of both h- and r-adaptivity, providing a hybrid (*hr*) approach, and is explored in depth here. This approach benefits from the h-adaptive ability to completely regenerate a mesh before it gains tangled nodes, as well as the r-adaptive ability to allow degrees of freedom to follow aspects of fluid flow, such as a tsunami wave. A hybrid mesh adaptive approach is ideal for tsunami problems, since a large portion of fluid flow, which we would like to accurately resolve, is clustered in a relatively small region of ocean, which itself moves as time progresses.

A standalone finite element shallow water solver is constructed for solving tsunami modelling problems, along with an anisotropic mesh adaptivity library capable of adaptation both to fields related to the flow (such as fluid speed) and as guided by adjoint solution data. By applying mesh adaptivity to shallow water problems, this work aims to efficiently generate numerical solutions to tsunami wave propagation problems. The case study of the tsunami which struck Fukushima, Japan, in 2011 is considered, wherein some leading tsunami waves reached the coast in just *ten minutes*. Numerical results indicate computational cost can be reduced, whilst retaining a sufficiently high accuracy, under mesh adaptivity. Through establishing a highly efficient approach to numerical tsunami simulation, sufficient warning could be provided in future scenarios, allowing for evacuation and damage mitigation in those coastal areas determined to be most at risk.

I hereby declare that this Masters thesis is entirely my own work and has not previously been submitted as part of another higher degree at any other university or institution. Wherever external sources have been used, references are provided in the bibliography.

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1. Preliminaries

1.1 Abbreviations

AMR: adaptive mesh refinement.

SPD: symmetric positive-definite.

DOF: degrees of freedom.

SW: shallow water.

FEM: finite element method.

SWEs: shallow water equations.

GIS: geographical information system.

UFL: unified form language.

PDE: partial differential equation.

UTM: universal transverse mercator.

1.2 Notation

The following items establish all pieces of notation used in this project which are not entirely standard in the literature.

- $\mathbb{N}_0 := \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\} = \{0, 1, 2, 3, \dots\}$ denotes the *natural numbers with zero included*.
- For functions $f : A \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and $\mathbf{u} : A \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ on $A \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n$,

$$\frac{\partial f}{\partial \mathbf{u}} := \left[\frac{\partial f}{\partial u_1} \quad \dots \quad \frac{\partial f}{\partial u_n} \right]^T : A \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n, \quad \text{with the gradient} \quad \frac{\partial f}{\partial \mathbf{x}} = \nabla f. \quad (1.1)$$

- For functions $\mathbf{f} : A \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^m$ and $\mathbf{u} : A \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ on $A \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n$,

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{f}}{\partial \mathbf{u}} := \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial f_1}{\partial u_1} & \dots & \frac{\partial f_1}{\partial u_n} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \frac{\partial f_m}{\partial u_1} & \dots & \frac{\partial f_m}{\partial u_n} \end{bmatrix} : A \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}, \quad (1.2)$$

provides the *Jacobian matrix* for the transformation from variables \mathbf{f} to variables \mathbf{u} .

The *Jacobian* $\frac{\partial \mathbf{f}}{\partial \mathbf{x}} = J(\mathbf{f})$, of \mathbf{f} provides a common example.

- If a matrix $A \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ is *positive definite* then we write $A \succ 0$.

- Given a metric space (X, d) , a subset $U \subseteq X$ thereof has *closure*

$$\bar{U} = \{x \in X \mid \forall \epsilon > 0, \exists y \in U \mid d(x, y) < \epsilon\},$$

interior $U^\circ = X \setminus \overline{(X \setminus U)}$ and *boundary* $\partial U = \bar{U} \setminus U^\circ$.

- We denote by I_n the $n \times n$ *identity matrix*, for $n \in \mathbb{N}$.
- Meshes are denoted by \mathcal{H} and contain three types of *entity*: (triangular) *elements* $K \subset \mathbb{R}^2$, *vertices* $\mathbf{p} \in \mathbb{R}^2$ and *edges* \mathbf{pq} , which are often also considered as vectors in \mathbb{R}^2 .
- Given some domain, P_k denotes a *degree- k piecewise polynomial function space* defined over the domain, where $k \in \mathbb{N}$. The same notation is used in vector and scalar cases, but the distinction is made clear.

1.3 Notes on computer resources

The majority of the computer code used in this project is written in Python, with incorporation of UFL in order to deal with forms. Additional computer packages used are listed below, along with web links for their download and associated documentation.

Firedrake: <http://firedrakeproject.org> **PRAgMaTic:** <https://github.com/meshadaptation/pragmatic>

GMSH: <http://gmsh.info>

QGIS: <http://www.qgis.org>

GMT: <http://gmt.soest.hawaii.edu>

Paraview: <http://www.paraview.org>

QMESH: [Avdis et al., 2017]

PlotDigitizer: <http://plotdigitizer.sourceforge.net>

Thetis: <http://thetisproject.org>

In addition, we make use of two geographic databases, referenced below.

GSHHG *Global Self-consistent, Hierarchical, High-resolution Geography:*
<http://www.soest.hawaii.edu/pwessel/gshhg/>

GEBCO *General Bathymetric Chart of the Oceans:* <http://www.gebco.net>

All Python code for this project can be found on GitHub, at the web address <https://github.com/jwallwork23/MResProject>. There can be found a number of Python scripts, whose roles are described in Section 5.7, along with directories containing data from the above sources and also plots.¹

¹Everything needed to run the code is included in the directories of the GitHub page, except for the mesh files. This is for copyrighting purposes, but the meshes can be provided upon request, with the permission of the QMESH developers.

2. Introduction

Figure 2.1: Interpretation of an adaptively meshes tsunami. Original image “*The Great Wave off Kanagawa*” by the Japanese artist Katsushika Hokusai (1830-1833) edited by the author.

The word *tsunami* derives from Japanese, where ‘tsu’ refers to the harbour and ‘nami’ refers to a sea wave [Lisitzin, 1974]. This language is suggestive of the serious damage that these waves wreak upon their arrival into harbours across Japan. In recent and ancient history, and in particular in Japan, tsunamis have proved to be natural disasters with devastating impacts on human civilisations. This kind of damaging tsunami are common in the seismically active Pacific rim near Japan’s coast, and as a country comprising a collection of small islands, Japan’s coastal cities particularly vulnerable. One of the most memorable tsunamis of recent times, and indeed the most powerful one to strike Japan on record, had its epicentre off the coast of Tōhoku and struck many parts of the country in 2011, including the Fukushima region.

The tsunami caused 15,893 deaths, much devastation to hundreds of thousands of homes and played a large part in causing the level 7 meltdown of the Fukushima Dai-ichi nuclear power plant.¹ Although the meltdown event itself caused no deaths, much disruption was caused; an enormous clean-up operation was required, and there was a mass-evacuation of over 160,000 people who lived within a 20 km radius, wherein the yearly dosage of radiation was expected to reach dangerous levels of 20 mSv year^{-1} in the years following the accident.² Only now, six years after the incident, is the radioactivity low enough to begin the clean-up, and still some robots are unable to handle the conditions. Preliminary and later reports of the earthquake, tsunami and following meltdown

¹Details obtained from the National Police Agency of Japan:
http://www.npa.go.jp/archive/keibi/biki/higaijokyo_e.pdf.

²For further details, see <http://fukushimaontheglobe.com>.

events include those by [Kazama and Noda, 2012], [Okada, 2011] and [Simons et al., 2011], with further analyses are provided by [Baba et al., 2017] and [Suzuki et al., 2012].

There is an obvious desire to avoid such occurrences in the future, and the Japanese government have even motioned to review its use of nuclear power in its energy grid due to the high risk of these extreme events. Yet in the light of the enormous problem posed by climate change, we should not be too hasty to abandon this relatively clean alternative to carbon dioxide-emitting fossil fuels which has the potential to generate vast amounts of electricity. An alternative approach to the problem is to make tsunami early-warning systems much more efficient.

This problem will be considered in this thesis, making use of adaptive meshes in numerical ocean modelling. Mesh adaptivity aims to discretise the domain of ocean of interest in an unstructured way, this not only varies in resolution spatially, but also adapts temporally. In this way, fluid dynamics near to the tsunami wave can be resolved more accurately, whilst minimising the computational effort expended on solving the flow equations in locations distant from both the wave and vulnerable coastal civilisations. The result is an efficient and yet relatively computationally cheap approach.

The mathematical model to which we apply the adaptive process is provided by the *shallow water equations*, which are well-known to provide a good approximation of large scale oceanic fluid dynamics. These equations may be solved using the *finite element method* which, unlike the *finite difference method*, has the advantage of working well on unstructured grids.

The central aim of this project is to construct an effective and efficient means of modelling the 2011 Tōhoku tsunami, which arrives at a solution within the 10 minute timeframe before the waves were first felt, and which sufficiently accurately resolves the coastal bound tsunami wave. Thus, by implementing such a method in the future, vulnerable regions may be given sufficient time to evacuate and damage may be mitigated. Throughout, we refer to the case study tsunami as the *Tōhoku tsunami*.

The structure of this thesis is as follows. Chapter 3 outlines the mathematical setup, including equations and initial and boundary conditions used. Chapter 4 then goes on to describe the solution approach to solving problems of the form described in Chapter 3 and outlines in brief the general procedure of anisotropic mesh adaptivity, with further detail provided in Chapter 5. Chapters 4 and 5 also include plots and results from the non-adaptive and adaptive algorithms applied to model tsunami problems, respectively. Finally, Chapter 6 uses the content of the preceding chapters to apply anisotropic mesh adaptivity to the Tōhoku tsunami case study, including some model verification and result comparisons with alternative solution approaches.

Figure 2.2: Gauge locations near Fukushima, courtesy of [Saito et al., 2011]. The star indicates the earthquake epicentre and small circles indicate aftershock locations.

3. Mathematical formulation

In this chapter, we introduce the fluid dynamical equation set used throughout this project for tsunami modelling, including boundary conditions and the associated *adjoint problem*.

3.1 Shallow water equations

Throughout this thesis $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^2$ denotes the spatial domain of interest, corresponding to a region of ocean, and T denotes the end-time of our simulation. The problem considered concerns a tsunami which occurs at sea, where the ocean depth is of the order of a few kilometres and its width is comparatively much larger (on the order of thousands of kilometres). Rather than working with the full *Navier-Stokes equations*, it therefore makes sense to work with the simplified *shallow water equations (SWEs)*, as mentioned in Chapter 2. These parabolic PDEs are derived from the Navier-Stokes equations by *depth-averaging* fluid velocity. Thus the fluid velocity is constrained to horizontal motion, with no vertical component.

Using the notation of [Funke et al., 2014], let $\mathbf{u} : \Omega \times (0, T] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$ denote depth-averaged velocity and $\eta : \Omega \times (0, T] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ denote free-surface displacement.¹ Total fluid depth is given by $h = \eta + b : \Omega \times (0, T] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, where $b : \Omega \rightarrow (0, \infty)$ is the bathymetry profile of the domain. A schematic of these variables and quantities is displayed in Figure 3.1. We use the usual notation of $g = 9.81 \text{ m s}^{-2}$ for gravitational acceleration, $\nu > 0$ for the diffusion coefficient and denote by $c_b : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ the (quadratic) bottom friction coefficient. In this notation, the (non-rotating) SWEs are given by [Funke et al., 2014]

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial t} + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \mathbf{u} - \nu \nabla^2 \mathbf{u} + g \nabla \eta + \frac{c_b}{h} \|\mathbf{u}\| \mathbf{u} = \mathbf{0}, \quad \frac{\partial \eta}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (h \mathbf{u}) = 0, \quad (3.1)$$

where $\nabla \cdot = (\partial_x \cdot, \partial_y \cdot)$ denotes gradients in the horizontal.

We have ignored the Coriolis effect, which manifests as a curl term $2\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{u}$, where $|\boldsymbol{\Omega}| = 7.2921 \times 10^{-5} \text{ rad s}^{-1}$ is Earth's rotation rate. We justify this omission by remarking on the vast differences in timescales on which tsunamis and the Coriolis-driven tides act: the Tōhoku tsunami reached much of the Japanese shoreline within *10-30 minutes*, while the period between high tides is *12-13 hours*. In Section 6.2, we perform numerical experiments to show omission of the Coriolis term is reasonable and makes little change

¹We often suppress the time dependence and write $\mathbf{q} = (\mathbf{u}, \eta) : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^3$.

Figure 3.1: A tikZ diagram illustrating the quantities and variables defining the SWEs.

to the resulting dynamics.

Solving a *linear* PDE by FEM amounts to solving linear systems, which is computationally cheaper than solving a nonlinear PDE, such as (3.1), which requires use of an iterative nonlinear solver, such as *Newton's method*. As such, it would be attractive for us to consider linearisation of the SWEs. Linearising (3.1) with respect to a flat surface $\eta(\mathbf{x}, t) = \bar{\eta}$ with zero velocity $\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \bar{\mathbf{u}} = \mathbf{0}$, we obtain

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial t} + g \nabla \eta = \mathbf{0}, \quad \frac{\partial \eta}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot ((\bar{\eta} + b) \mathbf{u}) = 0, \quad (3.2)$$

where the flat surface $\bar{\eta}$ is typically taken as zero. In Section 6.2 we illustrate how the accuracy of our solution is not significantly decreased by using (3.2), rather than (3.1), in the Tōhoku tsunami case.

The linear equations have the form of a hyperbolic vector PDE,

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \mathbf{q} + A_1 \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \mathbf{q} + A_2 \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \mathbf{q} = \mathbf{0}, \quad (3.3)$$

where

$$\mathbf{q} = \begin{bmatrix} u \\ v \\ \eta \end{bmatrix}, \quad A_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & \bar{\eta} + b \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ g & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad A_2 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \bar{\eta} + b \\ 0 & g & 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (3.4)$$

Here we have eigenvalue spectra $\Lambda(A_1) = \{0, \pm c\} = \Lambda(A_2)$, where $c^2 = g(\bar{\eta} + b) =: g\bar{h}$.

Following [Aydin, 2011], in the case of a flat bathymetry (whereby $\nabla b \equiv \mathbf{0}$) and provided $u, v, \eta \in C^2(\Omega)$, we can derive from (3.2) the PDE

$$\frac{\partial^2 \eta}{\partial t^2} - g(\bar{\eta} + b) \nabla^2 \eta = 0 \quad (3.5)$$

for η alone. This is a wave equation, which admits solutions of the form

$$\eta = \eta_0 e^{i(kx + \ell y - \omega t)}, \quad (3.6)$$

where k and ℓ denote wavenumbers in the respective x - and y -directions and ω denotes the wave frequency. Substituting (3.6) into the wave equation of (3.5), we derive the

dispersion relation

$$\omega = \pm \kappa \sqrt{g\bar{h}}, \quad (3.7)$$

where $\kappa = \sqrt{k^2 + \ell^2}$ denotes the *total wavenumber*.

Substituting (3.6) into (3.2), we find the linearised SWEs have wave-like solutions, termed *gravity waves*. For an initial free surface η_0 , these correspond to

$$\eta = \eta_0 e^{i(kx + \ell y \pm \kappa t \sqrt{g\bar{h}})}, \quad \mathbf{u} = \pm \frac{\eta_0 \sqrt{g}}{\kappa \sqrt{\bar{h}}} e^{i(kx + \ell y \pm \kappa t \sqrt{g\bar{h}})} \begin{bmatrix} k \\ \ell \end{bmatrix}, \quad \text{for } k, \ell \in \mathbb{N}. \quad (3.8)$$

This means a wave with wavenumber k oscillates in the x -direction with frequency $k\sqrt{g\bar{h}}$. The wave speed of such a wave is $\sqrt{g\bar{h}}$, implying gravity waves are *non-dispersive*.

In deriving the SWEs, we assume *hydrostatic balance*, which holds provided wavelength is greater than the vertical height scale. As such, the SW approximation is suitable for tsunami modelling due to the long length scales, and correspondingly short height scales, involved. The reason this wave speed value is important for the modelling of tsunamis is that, as the waves resulting from a tsunami approach the shore, \bar{h} becomes smaller due to the shallower water, meaning leading waves slow down relative to those following them. This results in constructive interference, causing the leading waves to become taller and taller, eventually resulting in the very tall waves characteristic of tsunamis. Where the ocean is around 4km deep, we have a wave speed of around $\sqrt{9.81 \times 4000} \approx 200\text{ms}^{-1}$, which is *very fast*.

3.2 Forward problem

In order to implement FEM, we require the PDE weak form. This is then discretised by considering functions as members of a finite dimensional function space W , and expanding over basis coefficients. For the SWEs, we consider a mixed formulation $W = V \times Z$ of vector and scalar function spaces, respectively. We use the continuous Galerkin method, whereby V and Z are piecewise polynomial function spaces P_k (for $k \in \mathbb{N}$), whose members are polynomial on each element of the mesh and continuous across their associated boundaries. In particular, we choose the *Taylor-Hood* function space pair, denoted P2–P1, noting that the former is a vector function space. This choice is made both for reasons of simplicity and because the standalone SW solver’s interpolation procedure, as considered in Section 5.7, only currently supports interpolation between continuous spaces.

As described in detail in [Brenner and Scott, 2007] and [Thoméé, 2006], through expanding test functions $\mathbf{v} \in V$ and $\zeta \in Z$ over function space bases, we may form a system of nonlinear equations which can be solved using Newton’s method. Since the equations (3.1) we consider are unsteady, we also need a means of time integration. For this, finite element solves are implemented at each step of a timestepping scheme, such as the *implicit Euler method*. Time integrators are briefly discussed in Section 4.3.

For purposes of solving using *Firedrake*, we have the *weak residual form*,

$$a(\mathbf{q}; \mathbf{w}) = 0, \quad \forall \mathbf{w} = (\mathbf{v}, \zeta) \in W = V \times Z, \quad \text{where } \mathbf{q} = (\mathbf{u}, \eta). \quad (3.9)$$

In the nonlinear case the *weak residual* is defined by summing the terms of the weak form:

$$\begin{aligned} a(\mathbf{q}; \mathbf{w}) = & \langle \mathbf{u}_t, \mathbf{v} \rangle_\Omega + \langle \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v} \rangle_\Omega + \nu \langle \nabla \mathbf{u}, \nabla \mathbf{v} \rangle_\Omega - \nu \langle \hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot \nabla \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v} \rangle_{\partial\Omega} + g \langle \nabla \eta, \mathbf{v} \rangle_\Omega \\ & + \left\langle \frac{c_b}{\eta + b} \|\mathbf{u}\| \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v} \right\rangle_\Omega + \langle \eta_t, \zeta \rangle_\Omega - \langle (\eta + b) \mathbf{u}, \nabla \zeta \rangle_\Omega + \langle (\eta + b) \mathbf{u} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}}, \zeta \rangle_{\partial\Omega}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.10)$$

By construction, every term in (3.9) is linear in the second argument, which contains test functions and the gradients thereof.

Some terms of (3.10) may be altered or dropped due to Neumann boundary conditions, if enforced as discussed in Section 3.3. Since V and Z are spanned by different basis functions, it makes sense to sum their components in the weak residual (3.10) and attempt to solve the consequent system of nonlinear equations.

In the linear case, (3.2) yields the weak residual

$$a(\mathbf{q}; \mathbf{w}) = \langle \mathbf{u}_t, \mathbf{v} \rangle_\Omega + g \langle \nabla \eta, \mathbf{v} \rangle_\Omega + \langle \eta_t, \zeta \rangle_\Omega - \langle (\eta + b) \mathbf{u}, \nabla \zeta \rangle_\Omega + \langle (\eta + b) \mathbf{u} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}}, \zeta \rangle_{\partial\Omega}, \quad (3.11)$$

As mentioned in Section 3.1, (3.9) gives rise to a *linear* system under (3.11), so Newton's method need not be invoked and we can instead invoke efficient algorithms of numerical linear algebra.

3.3 Boundary conditions

The test problems we consider in Section 5.8 have tank domains, with impermeable walls. This property is manifested in the boundary conditions by the enforcement of a zero flux boundary condition by $\mathbf{u} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}}|_{\partial\Omega} = 0$, where $\hat{\mathbf{n}}$ denotes the outward-pointing normal for each section. Here there is no inflow or outflow boundary, and the zero flux condition means we also apply the Neumann boundary condition $(\hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{u}|_{\partial\Omega} = \mathbf{0}$, so that the gradient of the normal component of velocity is also zero at the boundaries. Neumann conditions such as these are straightforward to implement in the FEM, since they merely require the omission of some boundary terms from the weak residual (3.10) or (3.11).

In the oceanic tsunami case, these boundary conditions are not particularly realistic, especially at open ocean boundaries. As such, for the Tōhoku problem we may wish to consider alternative boundary conditions, or implement a *wetting and drying* algorithm.

3.4 Adjoint problem

As mentioned in Chapter 2, this project concerns *mesh-adaptivity*, which will be outlined in Section 4.1 and explained in detail in Chapter 5. For the purpose of implementing *goal-based* mesh adaptivity – considered in Section 5.9 – we require the *adjoint problem* to the forward problem described above. Let $X := \{\mathbf{f} : \Omega \times (0, T] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^3\}$ denote the space of all 3-vector functions defined on our spatio-temporal domain. Consider a scalar functional $J : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ which depends on the SW solution tuple $\mathbf{q} = (\mathbf{u}, \eta) \in X$ and denote the image of \mathbf{q} by $\Omega_s \subseteq \mathbb{R}^3$. Here J provides some measure of a quantity related to the forward problem solution over a time range $t \in [T_{\text{start}}, T_{\text{end}}] \subseteq [0, T]$. We seek to minimise the error made in our computation of this quantity J , thereby providing accurate information regarding some *important* aspect of the dynamics. In the following, we take ideas from [Blaise et al., 2013], [Funke et al., 2014] and, most notably, [Davis and LeVeque, 2016].

By concatenating the SWEs (3.1) describing the ocean flow, we may construct a *residual* operator $\mathcal{R} : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^3$ which yields the *canonical equation*

$$\mathcal{R}(\mathbf{q}) = \mathbf{0}, \tag{3.12}$$

determining whether the physical requirements are met.² That is, the SWEs are solved when (3.12) is satisfied, subject to appropriate initial and boundary conditions. Note the similarity to the weak residual form (3.9) of the weak problem. Our aim is to minimise the residual $\mathcal{R}(\mathbf{q})$ at each timestep, *in some sense* further described in Section 5.9.

For a functional $f : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, consider a functional of the form

$$J(\mathbf{q}) = \int_{T_{\text{start}}}^{T_{\text{end}}} \int_{\Omega_s} f(\mathbf{q}) \, dx \, dt. \tag{3.13}$$

A common choice is to take $f(\mathbf{q}; \mathbf{x}, t) = \mathbf{k}(\mathbf{x})^T \mathbf{q}(\mathbf{x}, t)$, where $\mathbf{k} : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^3$ is some kernel expressing the relationship between J and the solution tuple \mathbf{q} . Let $A \subset \Omega$ correspond to the coastal region of highest importance. Giving $\mathbf{k}(\mathbf{x}) = (0, 0, \mathbb{1}_A(\mathbf{x}))$ the form of an indicator function allows us to consider the free surface displacement near to Daiichi nuclear power plant, say. We integrate over time as well as space because we do not know *a priori* at what time the tsunami wave will arrive in the important region. However we assume that the tsunami will not reach the coast before time $t = T_{\text{start}}$, and all waves will have entered the region by $t = T_{\text{end}}$. In practice, we usually take $T_{\text{end}} = T$.

Given the canonical form of (3.12), the corresponding *adjoint equation* is given by

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{R}^*}{\partial \mathbf{q}} \boldsymbol{\lambda} = \frac{\partial J^*}{\partial \mathbf{q}}, \tag{3.14}$$

where $*$ denotes the Hermitian operator. As in [Funke et al., 2014], the notation $\boldsymbol{\lambda}$ is

²In the case of linear SW, this is a linear operator.

used for the adjoint solution, because it plays the role of a Lagrange multiplier which enforces the PDE constraint upon the optimisation problem. As outlined in Appendix C of [Funke, 2012], the adjoint form is found in three steps, as follows. First, take the derivative of (3.12) in direction $\mathbf{w} = (\mathbf{w}_u, w_\eta) \in W = V \times Z$ to establish $\frac{\partial \mathcal{R}}{\partial \mathbf{q}} \mathbf{w}$. Secondly, consider the weak formulation of finding $\boldsymbol{\lambda} \in W$ such that

$$\left\langle \frac{\partial \mathcal{R}^*}{\partial \mathbf{q}} \boldsymbol{\lambda}, \mathbf{w} \right\rangle_\Omega = \left\langle \boldsymbol{\lambda}, \frac{\partial \mathcal{R}}{\partial \mathbf{q}} \mathbf{w} \right\rangle_\Omega = \left\langle \frac{\partial J^*}{\partial \mathbf{q}}, \mathbf{w} \right\rangle_\Omega, \quad \forall \mathbf{w} \in W \quad (3.15)$$

and integrate by parts so that \mathbf{w} is isolated on the right hand side of each inner product. From (3.15), we are able to deduce the strong form of the adjoint problem.

In our case, the procedure outlined above yields the functional gradient and adjoint solution appearing in the formulation of shallow water *adjoint problem* as

$$\begin{aligned} -\frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\lambda}_u}{\partial t} + (\nabla \mathbf{u})^* \boldsymbol{\lambda}_u - (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}) \boldsymbol{\lambda}_u - \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \boldsymbol{\lambda}_u - \nu \nabla^2 \boldsymbol{\lambda}_u - \nabla(h\lambda_\eta) + \frac{C_b}{h} \left(\|\mathbf{u}\| \boldsymbol{\lambda}_u + \frac{\mathbf{u} \cdot \boldsymbol{\lambda}_u}{\|\mathbf{u}\|} \mathbf{u} \right) &= \frac{\partial J^*}{\partial \mathbf{u}}, \\ -\frac{\partial \lambda_\eta}{\partial t} - g \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\lambda}_u &= \frac{\partial J^*}{\partial \eta}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.16)$$

Here boundary conditions have been carefully chosen such that the adjoint formulation provided by (3.16) includes no boundary terms. Note that the adjoint problem is solved *backwards* in time, since its solution is related to the sensitivity of the forward solution upon (3.13). Notice equations (3.16) depend on J , meaning the adjoint solution depends not only on the forward solution but also on the choice of functional.

Due to the linear hyperbolic form of (3.3), the adjoint form is given by

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \boldsymbol{\lambda} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} (A_1^T \boldsymbol{\lambda}) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} (A_2^T \boldsymbol{\lambda}) = -\frac{\partial J^*}{\partial \mathbf{q}}, \quad (3.17)$$

recalling both matrices vary spatially. Writing (3.17) out explicitly, we obtain

$$-\frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\lambda}_u}{\partial t} - b \nabla \lambda_\eta - \lambda_\eta \nabla b = \frac{\partial J^*}{\partial \mathbf{u}}, \quad -\frac{\partial \lambda_\eta}{\partial t} - g \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\lambda}_u = \frac{\partial J^*}{\partial \eta}, \quad (3.18)$$

as we expect when omitting the necessary terms in (3.16).

3.5 Finite element problem solving by computer

The Python library *Firedrake* provides a means of solving PDEs using FEM, with many choices of discretisation. The user runs code in Python, incorporating UFL - designed specifically for working with finite element problems as part of the FEniCS project - and the code itself is interpreted and compiled in C. For time dependent problems, the solution over time is obtained by time-stepping as described in Section 4.3, updating solution variables and thereby solving the FEM problem for the new time-step.

4. Methodology and an idealised experiment

In this chapter we outline and evaluate the general concept of anisotropic mesh adaptivity, which is explained in more detail in Chapter 5, along with the framework within which we solve PDEs using this process. In addition, we consider a model 1D problem to interpret the *adjoint problem* concept, hinting at how this could prove useful in guiding adaptivity.

4.1 Mesh-adaptive process

A fixed mesh defined on a domain Ω has a spatially fixed set of DOFs. If these DOFs are not suitably distributed, or if the problem varies temporally, computational inefficiencies may become apparent. Whilst aiming to avoid such inefficiencies, we would also like to retain a suitably accurate approximation to the true dynamics. As such, it makes sense to consider a finer mesh where our approximation is deemed as poor and a coarser mesh where it is already of a high quality. This is precisely the approach of mesh adaptivity. Of course, we generally do not know the true error made in our approximation. Hence, to perform mesh adaptivity, we must have a means of *error estimation*.

Moreover, an adaptive mesh varies in time as well as space, meaning the mesh used may change across timesteps, as illustrated in Figure 4.1. The sequence $\{r_k\}_{k \in \mathbb{N}} \subseteq \mathbb{N}_0$ determines those timesteps in which the mesh is regenerated, which could also be selected adaptively, but which is incremented uniformly in this work.

The ability to work with adaptive meshes is particularly attractive for tsunami modelling, where the region of interest (surrounding the coast-bound tsunami wave) moves rather rapidly as time progresses. The task is to ensure both that the path of the tsunami is sufficiently resolved and also the part of the domain containing the wake of the wave becomes more coarsely meshed as it moves away, reducing computational cost.

Figure 4.1: The mesh-adaptive process.

Additionally, we would like to mesh finely near to locations of interest, such as densely populated areas, busy harbours and nuclear power plants.

The mesh-adaptive process contains three crucial steps: error estimation, mesh adaption and interpolation, as described in the following subsections.

4.1.1 Error estimation

In solving PDEs using FEM we often use P1 approximation, as for the free surface displacement in the SWEs in Chapter 3. For this function space, FEM theory as in [Brenner and Scott, 2007] provides the *Taylor remainder theorem* approximation error result

$$\epsilon_{\mathcal{A}} = \gamma \mathbf{v}^T |H| \mathbf{v}, \quad (4.1)$$

where $\gamma = \mathcal{O}(1)$ is a scalar, $\mathbf{v} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is a vector corresponding to a direction and magnitude and H is the Hessian of the solution field. As such, it makes sense to consider error estimates for the adaptive process based on the Hessian, described in detail in Chapter 5.

4.1.2 Mesh adaption

Having constructed error measures, the next task is to modify the mesh accordingly, providing the *mesh adaption*. There are various flavours of adaptivity, each with a different approach to this mesh adaption stage. Approaches include *p-adaptivity*, *h-adaptivity* and *r-adaptivity*. We are mainly interested in the latter two approaches. *Adaptive mesh refinement (AMR)* is a popular type of h-adaptivity. For a summary of the approaches of AMR and p-adaptivity, see [Behrens and Bader, 2009] and [Giorgiani et al., 2013], respectively. The cases of h- and r-adaptivity are evaluated in Section 4.2.

It is also possible to consider combinations of some of these approaches, as discussed in Section 4.2. While the purpose of the previous stage was to flag parts of the mesh for editing, the adaption phase seeks to perform these modifications.

4.1.3 Interpolation of solution

Once mesh adaption has been implemented, the final task is to interpolate the solution from the ‘*old mesh*’ onto the ‘*new mesh*’, providing another opportunity for accruing error. As such, central to h-adaptive methods is the concept of interpolation error

$$\epsilon_{\mathcal{I}} = \|\mathbf{q} - \Pi_h \mathbf{q}\|, \quad \text{in some norm } \|\cdot\| : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}, \quad (4.2)$$

where again $X = \{\mathbf{f} : \Omega \times (0, T] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^3\} \ni \mathbf{q}$. Interpolation error is made upon approximating the exact solution \mathbf{q} by some interpolant $\Pi_h \mathbf{q}$ over the mesh, in our case a Lagrange interpolant. Interpolation error does not arise in r-adaptivity, for reasons discussed in Section 4.2.

4.2 Evaluation of h- and r-adaptive approaches

As detailed in Section 5.2, h-adaptivity gauges mesh quality via a functional (5.15) and adapts according to a *metric*. This SPD tensor field depends on the Hessian of the solution field, in accordance with (4.1). In h-adaptivity, mesh entities may be created or destroyed, thus altering the mesh topology, whilst r-adaptivity fixes the mesh topology, with entities simply moving around the domain, as determined by another functional.

The h-adaptive procedure repeatedly evaluates the quality functional following various geometrical and topological operations upon the mesh, aiming towards its minimisation, whereby the mesh has desirable properties. Historically, h-adaptivity is usually considered on Cartesian meshes and the ‘h’ refers to the h which usually denotes the size of elements used in FEM. Altering mesh topology can require an excessive amount of interpolation and pose an issue for our problem, since the region surrounding the tsunami, which requires finer resolution, moves with the flow. Excessive interpolation contributes to a heightened computational cost, which is completely against our motive of pursuing adaptive meshing in order to create a more efficient algorithm. This motivates considering the idea of a *moving mesh* which is able to *chase the wave*, leaving coarser mesh in its wake.

The approach of *r-adaptivity* is indeed often referred to as *mesh movement* and can provide a more effective approach for cases in which regions of increased resolution move with the flow. The ‘r’ of r-adaptivity comes from the *relocation* of the mesh nodes, which can be achieved in a number of ways, discussed in [Piggott et al., 2005]: a variational approach makes use of the Euler-Lagrange equations; it is also possible to apply a so-called *mesh smoothing* algorithm in order to achieve mesh movement. As noted in [Piggott et al., 2005], the fact r-adaptivity moves the mesh with the flow has the result of reducing large transport velocities, such as those associated with the tsunami. This means there are fewer timestep restrictions than for application of h-adaptivity, providing a clear numerical advantage. On the other hand, unlike with h-adaptivity where new nodes can be created, r-adaptive methods hold the DOF count constant, potentially leading to problems if the dynamics of the problem at hand become rather complex. In these situations, it would be advantageous to be able to ‘inject’ mesh resolution into a certain region – something which is not available in r-adaptivity. In addition, r-adaptivity can produce problematic, so-called ‘*tangled meshes*’, whereby two or more elements overlap.

Clearly, there are disadvantages to the approaches of both h- and r-adaptivity, but it appears that many of these are complemented by corresponding advantages for the other approach. As suggested above, it is both desirable and possible to combine the two, yielding a hybrid, *hr-adaptive* method. One such approach, as described in [Habashi et al., 2000], is to incorporate a moving mesh within a mesh optimisation method such as described earlier. Alternately, h-adaptivity can be incorporated within the structure of moving meshes on a local scale, as in [Lang et al., 2003], to ensure elements are not poorly shaped and neither is the specified error tolerance reached.

4.3 Time integration

As discussed in Chapter 3, solution of the SWEs requires timestepping, with FEM solves at each iteration. Two candidate timestepping schemes are described in the following.

For the purposes of these analyses, consider a simple PDE problem

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = f(u(t), t), \quad u(0) = u_0 \quad (4.3)$$

defined on some domain $\Omega \subseteq \mathbb{R}$, for a dependent variable $u : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, forcing term $f : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and initial value $u_0 \in \mathbb{R}$. Suppose we have a uniform time discretisation $\{u^{(n)}\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}_0}$ of the dependent variable, with (constant) timestep $\Delta t > 0$.

One approach is the *implicit Euler method*, whereby the value of u at the current timestep depends on information available only at the current timestep:

$$\frac{u^{(n+1)} - u^{(n)}}{\Delta t} = f(u^{(n+1)}, t^{(n+1)}). \quad (4.4)$$

Whilst this equation is not as straightforward to solve as with explicit methods, amounting to solving a matrix system, it has the advantage of having a large region of absolute stability. However this approach is only $\mathcal{O}(\Delta t)$ at a particular time t and does not conserve energy. We would prefer to use a higher order, conservative time integrator.

In (4.4), the forcing function f is evaluated only at current time values. Another approach is to evaluate at an intermediate time, say halfway between the previous and current timesteps. From this we derive the *implicit midpoint rule*, given by

$$\frac{u^{(n+1)} - u^{(n)}}{\Delta t} = f\left(\frac{u^{(n+1)} + u^{(n)}}{2}, t^{(n)} + \frac{\Delta t}{2}\right). \quad (4.5)$$

Whilst more computationally expensive than (4.4), this approach has a global error of $\mathcal{O}(\Delta t^2)$, meaning the error decays quicker as we consider smaller timesteps. Further, (4.5) is a symplectic integrator in the context of Hamiltonian dynamics, so conserves energy.

For *explicit* time integrators, the spatio-temporal discretisation used must satisfy the *Courant-Friedrichs-Levy (CFL) condition* (established in [Courant et al., 1928]),

$$c := \Delta t \left(\frac{|u|}{\Delta x} + \frac{|v|}{\Delta y} \right) \leq 1, \quad (4.6)$$

for stability. Since (4.4) and (4.5) are *implicit* integrators, this condition can be broken without incurring penalties of reduced stability. However, it is still useful to make use of (4.6) when choosing a timestep length. We showed in Section 3.1 that the wave speed of a linear SW wave is given by $\sqrt{g\bar{h}}$, where \bar{h} is the water depth when at rest. As such, for the SWEs, $|u|, |v| \leq \sqrt{gb_{\max}}$, where b_{\max} denotes the maximal bathymetry in Ω . In selecting a timestep length, we should ensure it is sufficiently less than the ratio of the minimum tolerated element size and twice this upper bound for the component speeds.

4.4 One-dimensional tsunami test problem

As a first model SW problem, consider the idealised 1D tsunami problem described in [Davis and LeVeque, 2016]. This problem concerns propagation of an initial surface profile caused by a tsunami across a simplified ocean domain of width 400 km. The domain bathymetry b has a shelf break discontinuity, as illustrated in Subfigure 4.2a:

$$b(x) = \begin{cases} 200 \text{ m} & x \leq 50 \text{ km} \\ 4,000 \text{ m} & x > 50 \text{ km} \end{cases}. \quad (4.7)$$

Illustrated in Subfigure 4.2b, the initial condition used is given by

$$\eta_0(x) = \begin{cases} 0.4 \sin\left(\frac{(x-100,000)\pi}{50,000}\right) \text{ m} & 100 \text{ km} \leq x \leq 150 \text{ km} \\ 0 \text{ m} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}. \quad (4.8)$$

As in Section 3.3, (unrealistic) impermeable boundaries are considered, whereby $u(4 \cdot 10^5) = u(0) = 0$. This means waves simply reflect off both the coastal and open ocean boundaries. The 1D form of the SWEs used in [Davis and LeVeque, 2016] take an alternative linear form

$$\mu_t + g\bar{h}(x)\eta_x = 0, \quad \eta_t + \mu_x = 0, \quad (4.9)$$

where $\mu = hu$ represents momentum and we have (again) linearised about a flat surface $\bar{\eta}$ with zero velocity $\bar{u} = 0$. As with (3.3), (4.9) may be written in matrix-vector form

$$\mathbf{q}_t + A(x)\mathbf{q}_x = \mathbf{0}, \quad \text{where} \quad A(x) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & g\bar{h}(x) \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{q} = \begin{bmatrix} \mu \\ \eta \end{bmatrix}. \quad (4.10)$$

In `1D_tsunami_test.py`, we also consider the adjoint problem. Given the equation of (4.10), as outlined in [Davis and LeVeque, 2016], test by an appropriately sized vector functional $\boldsymbol{\lambda}$ and integrate over the spatio-temporal domain to obtain

$$\int_0^{4 \cdot 10^5} \int_0^{4200} \boldsymbol{\lambda}^T(\mathbf{q}_t + A\mathbf{q}_x) dt dx = 0. \quad (4.11)$$

Figure 4.2: Bathymetry and ‘initial’ conditions used for the 1D tsunami test problem.

Integrating by parts in both space and time,

$$\int_0^{4 \cdot 10^5} (\boldsymbol{\lambda}^T \mathbf{q}) \Big|_0^{4200} dx + \int_0^T (\boldsymbol{\lambda}^T A \mathbf{q}) \Big|_0^{4 \cdot 10^5} dt - \int_0^{4 \cdot 10^5} \int_0^{4200} \mathbf{q}^T (\boldsymbol{\lambda}_t + (A^T \boldsymbol{\lambda})_x) dx = 0. \quad (4.12)$$

We consider an objective functional *only at the end time*, with $T_{\text{start}} = T_{\text{end}} = T$, so the integrand of the third term of (4.12) contains the adjoint equation for this problem,

$$\boldsymbol{\lambda}_t + (A^T(x) \boldsymbol{\lambda})_x = 0, \quad \text{where } \boldsymbol{\lambda} = \begin{bmatrix} \lambda_\mu & \lambda_\eta \end{bmatrix}^T. \quad (4.13)$$

We enforce an ‘initial condition’ of the adjoint problem, as a scaled indicator function $\boldsymbol{\lambda}_{\eta,0}(x) = 0.4 \mathbb{1}_{[10 \text{ km}, 25 \text{ km}]}$, which approximates a corresponding delta function, as illustrated in Subfigure 4.2c. Again, we impose the boundary condition $\lambda_u(4 \cdot 10^5) = \lambda_u(0) = 0$. Since the adjoint equation is solved *backwards* in time, we transform time by $t \mapsto 4200 - t$, whence $\partial_t \mapsto -\partial_t$. Under the same boundary conditions, (4.13) becomes

$$\boldsymbol{\lambda}_t - (A^T(x) \boldsymbol{\lambda})_x = 0. \quad (4.14)$$

As in [Davis and LeVeque, 2016], we interpret these data by establishing regions of ocean where the forward and adjoint free surface solutions take numerical values with magnitude above some tolerance, say 0.05m, with resulting plots displayed in Subfigures 4.3a and 4.3b, respectively. The plots include a dashed line marking the location, 50 km offshore, of the shelf break discontinuity in bathymetry. Significant regions of the forward problem can be interpreted as areas of ocean to which the initial condition will propagate, whilst the adjoint significance regions, on the other hand, correspond to some approximation of the ‘*domain of dependence*’ wherein tsunami wave propagative activity will have an effect on the near-coastal area of importance at the end-time of the simulation.

Another interpretation may be gleaned by considering regions of ocean wherein the inner product between forward and adjoint problem solutions is significant, as displayed in Subfigure 4.3c. Thus, we gain information concerning which tsunami trajectories are important for our particular problem, giving a first suggestion of where mesh adaption should be performed. Notice the only important regions lie between coast and shelf break.

Figure 4.3: Regions of ocean where where orward and adjoint shallow water solutions (and the inner product thereof) have magnitude at least 0.05 m for the 1D tsunami test problem.

5. Anisotropic mesh adaptivity

When a mesh is regenerated using *anisotropic mesh adaptivity*, the goal is to improve the quality of the *worst* element of the mesh, in a local sense. In 2D, this is achieved by a performing some combination of the following operations.

1. edge splitting;
2. edge collapsing;
3. edge swapping;
4. node movement.

In the former three operations, the approach embodies that of h-adaptivity and in the latter operation it embodies that of r-adaptivity, thereby providing a variant of hr-adaptivity.

An optimisation algorithm loops over the nodes of the mesh, and uses the above operations to propose a new local mesh configuration, based on error measures as mentioned in Subsection 4.1.1. If certain criteria are satisfied, insisting the mesh quality is improved sufficiently across meshes (so it is worth the computational effort associated with regenerating the mesh), the new configuration is accepted. The means of measuring *mesh quality* is described in Section 5.2, with an alternative approach found in [Pain et al., 2001]. Further intricacies of the mesh adaptive process are also outlined in this chapter.

5.1 Measuring distance

A *scalar product* is defined as an SPD form, which can be represented by an SPD matrix M , known as a *metric*. Henceforth in this project, we work solely in 2D and so all meshes \mathcal{H} can be understood as subsets of \mathbb{R}^2 . As such, for our purposes, a metric provides a map

$$\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle_M : \mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow [0, \infty), \quad \langle \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y} \rangle_M = \mathbf{x}^T M \mathbf{y}, \quad \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{R}^2. \quad (5.1)$$

Euclidean space \mathbb{E}^2 is obtained by equipping a vector space with such a scalar product.

Given the scalar product defined by (5.1), we obtain the corresponding norm by

$$\| \cdot \|_M : \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow [0, \infty), \quad \| \mathbf{x} \|_M = \sqrt{\mathbf{x}^T M \mathbf{x}}, \quad \mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^2. \quad (5.2)$$

Lengths of mesh edges $\mathbf{pq} \in \mathcal{H}$ can be calculated using (5.2). As commented in [Barral, 2015], angles between vectors can also be computed in the usual way, with the angle $\theta \in [0, 2\pi)$ between two vectors $\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{R}^2$ with respect to a metric M given by

$$\cos \theta = \frac{\langle \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y} \rangle_M}{\| \mathbf{x} \|_M \| \mathbf{y} \|_M}. \quad (5.3)$$

Further, given an element K of the mesh has area $|K|_{I_2}$ with respect to \mathbb{E}^2 , its corresponding area in the metric space defined by M can be found using the determinant:

$$|K|_M = \sqrt{\det(M)}|K|_{I_2}. \quad (5.4)$$

As M is symmetric, it is *orthogonally diagonalisable*, with eigenvalue decomposition

$$M = V^T \Lambda V = \begin{bmatrix} u_1 & v_1 \\ u_2 & v_2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \lambda_1 & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda_2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} u_1 & u_2 \\ v_1 & v_2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.5)$$

where $\lambda_1, \lambda_2 > 0$, and eigenvectors $\mathbf{u} = [u_1, u_2]^T$ and $\mathbf{v} = [v_1, v_2]^T$ are orthonormal.

Combining the above ingredients, we come to an alternative understanding of a metric M in terms of geometry. That is, M can be described in terms of ellipses, with its eigenvectors determining the axes in which the ellipse is skewed and the inverse square root of its eigenvalues determining the magnitudes of skew along these axes. In the process of mesh adaption, we

Figure 5.1: The mapping of an ellipse to the unit circle under a metric.

seek to obtain a *uniform mesh* with respect to a metric. Let h_1 and h_2 denote the magnitudes of the ellipse axes. Then, for the unit vector $\mathbf{e}_1 = [1, 0]^T \in \mathbb{R}^2$,

$$\|h_1 \mathbf{e}_1\|_M^2 = \begin{bmatrix} h_1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} V^T \Lambda V \begin{bmatrix} h_1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = h_1^2 \lambda_1 = 1 \iff \lambda_1 = \frac{1}{h_1^2}, \quad (5.6)$$

using (5.5), and similarly for the second standard unit vector, $\mathbf{e}_2 = [0, 1]^T$. The metric achieves its purpose of controlling the mesh adaption process by defining the mesh edge lengths we desire at each node of the mesh. In tune with (5.6), for each eigenpair $(\lambda_i, \mathbf{v}_i)$ of M , we take the corresponding edge length in direction \mathbf{v}_i , as determined by

$$h_i = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\lambda_i}}. \quad (5.7)$$

Figure 5.1 depicts an ellipse with axes in directions given by the eigenvectors and magnitude given by the inverse square eigenvalues. Application of the square root $M^{\frac{1}{2}}$ of the metric then yields a unit circle (with axes being the standard unit vectors). Here the matrix square root is well-defined since all eigenvalues are positive, meaning we can take the square root through the eigenvalue decomposition,

$$M^{\frac{1}{2}} = V^T \Lambda^{\frac{1}{2}} V = V^T \text{diag}(\sqrt{\lambda_1}, \sqrt{\lambda_2}) V. \quad (5.8)$$

To contrast, in *isotropic* mesh adaptivity, metrics M are not only SPD, but diagonal,

taking the form $M = \text{diag}(h^{-2}, h^{-2})$ for some edge length $h > 0$. As such, the isotropic approach allows only changes in the size of elements, and not their orientation.

The scalar product provided in the Euclidean case by (5.1) is constant across the domain, so distances are measured using the same ellipse, regardless of location. As remarked in [Barral, 2015], it is attractive to be able to measure distances in a way dependent on the location within the domain. This is particularly so for tsunami propagation modelling, enabling us to consider mesh elements which have different sizes, using a fine mesh where high resolution is required and a coarse mesh in ‘less important’ regions.

For spatially dependent metrics, we consider *Riemannian*, rather than Euclidean, geometry. We now consider not just one SPD matrix M , but a space $\mathcal{M} = \{M_{\mathbf{x}}\}_{\mathbf{x} \in \Omega}$ thereof, defined on *all points of the domain*. Locally, each of these metrics defines a scalar product when evaluated on a point $\mathbf{x} \in \Omega$. Using these scalar products, we can establish a *Riemannian metric space*, to which we can extend notions of distance and angle from the Euclidean case. The following extends definitions as in [Pain et al., 2001].

For an element K of the mesh, consider one of its edges $e = \mathbf{pq} \in E_K$, with endpoints $\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q} \in \mathbb{R}^2$. The length of e with respect to metric \mathcal{M} is calculated analytically as

$$\ell_{\mathcal{M}}(e) = \int_0^1 \sqrt{\mathbf{pq}^T \mathcal{M}(\mathbf{p} + t\mathbf{pq}) \mathbf{pq}} dt \approx \sum_{i=1}^k \omega_i \sqrt{\mathbf{pq}^T \mathcal{M}(\mathbf{p} + \alpha_i \mathbf{pq}) \mathbf{pq}}, \quad (5.9)$$

using the notation of [Alauzet, 2010]. While the strict equality in (5.9) provides a continuous measure of distance along an edge, we need consider a discretised metric $\mathcal{M}_h = \{M_{\mathbf{p}}\}_{\mathbf{p} \in \mathcal{H}}$, as evaluated at the vertices of the mesh \mathcal{H} . Thus we consider a k -point quadrature rule with weights $\{\omega_i\}_{i=1}^k$ and Gauss points $\{\alpha_i\}_{i=1}^k$, as in the approximate equality of (5.9). In P1 space, there is linear variation within each element. As such, we consider linear variation of the discretised metric along each edge of the mesh, meaning it is sufficient to calculate length using one-point quadrature, as in [Piggott et al., 2005]:

$$\ell_{M_e}(e) = \|\mathbf{pq}\|_{M_e} = \sqrt{\mathbf{pq}^T M_e \mathbf{pq}}, \quad \text{where } M_e = \frac{1}{2}(M_{\mathbf{p}} + M_{\mathbf{q}}) \quad (5.10)$$

denotes the *edge-centred metric*, summed at the endpoints of e . That is, $\alpha_1 = \frac{1}{2}$ is the single Gauss point. Vertex-wise metrics are calculated using interpolation between meshes. Since $\mathcal{M}(\mathbf{x}) \succ 0, \forall \mathbf{x} \in \Omega$, in particular $M_{\mathbf{p}}, M_{\mathbf{q}} \succ 0$. Application of the definition of positive-definiteness implies $M_{\mathbf{p}} + M_{\mathbf{q}} \succ 0$, meaning the edge-centred metric is also positive-definite, for each edge of the mesh.

Similarly to (5.4), the area of an element K in Riemannian metric space $\mathcal{M} = \{M_{\mathbf{p}}\}_{\mathbf{p} \in \Omega}$ is given by the integral

$$|K|_{\mathcal{M}} = \int_K \sqrt{\det(\mathcal{M}(x, y))} dx dy. \quad (5.11)$$

As remarked in [Barral, 2015], this may be approximated to first order using (5.4), with

M replaced by \mathcal{M} applied at the barycentre of K . With the same modification, (5.3) can be used to calculate the angle between vectors \mathbf{u}_1 and \mathbf{u}_2 in the Riemannian metric space.

As already mentioned, the idea of metric-based mesh adaption, as first introduced in [George et al., 1991], is for the Riemannian metric space to be used in computing geometrical quantities which arrange for the new mesh to be a *unit mesh* with respect to this metric space. This links with the earlier interpretation of moving from an ellipse to a unit circle, in terms of the metric considered. As defined in [Alauzet and Loseille, 2016], K is a *unit element* if each of its sides have unit length with respect to the governing metric. Hence, $K \in \mathcal{H}$ is a unit element if and only if K is equilateral with all sides equal to 1. By basic trigonometry, such a triangle has area $\frac{\sqrt{3}}{4}$ with respect to M , and hence Euclidean area $\frac{\sqrt{3}}{4}(\det(M))^{-\frac{1}{2}}$. If we are to consider unit meshes as consisting purely of unit elements, it is clear most domains cannot be filled particularly well. For example, in Euclidean space, where $M = I_2$, a square cannot be filled with equilateral triangles without a number of gaps. It can, however, be filled using right angled triangles.

Due to the above, it is necessary for us to relax the constraint that our meshes contain only unit elements. Instead, as in [Barral, 2015], we consider a mesh which contains only *quasi-unit elements*, whose edges each have length in the range $[\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}, \sqrt{2}]$. In the Riemannian setting, (5.7) carries over to provide a measure of size,

$$h_{\mathcal{M}}(\mathbf{v}) = \frac{\|\mathbf{v}\|_2}{\ell_{\mathcal{M}}(\mathbf{v})}, \quad (5.12)$$

with respect to $\mathbf{v} \in \mathbb{R}^2$, which may be approximated using quadrature as in (5.10).

5.2 Gauging mesh quality

Consider a vector $\mathbf{J} \in \mathbb{R}^N$, where N denotes the number of elements on the current mesh, which will likely change value a number of times during a h-adaptive algorithm. We follow [Piggott et al., 2005] in measuring global mesh quality using the ∞ -norm,

$$\mathcal{F} = \|\mathbf{J}\|_{\infty}. \quad (5.13)$$

The use of an ∞ -norm means the mesh as a whole is held to have the quality of the *worst quality* element of the mesh, which we would like to improve, in a local sense.

The functional we consider coincides with the one used in *PRAgMaTic* (*Parallel anisotRopic Adaptive Mesh ToolKit*).¹, which provides anisotropic mesh adaptivity in Fire-drake for meshes of simplexes and which underpins the code written in this project. In

¹Quality functional information described in this section was collected from the associated GitHub page referenced in Section 1.3, in the `introduction.tex` file of the `docs` directory.

PRAgMaTic and in this project, the (local) element quality is measured by

$$J_K = \underbrace{12\sqrt{3} \frac{|K|_M}{|\partial K|_M^2}}_I f \left(\underbrace{\frac{|\partial K|_M}{3}}_{II} \right), \quad (5.14)$$

in the 2D case, as proposed by [Vasilevskii and Lipnikov, 1999]. Here $|\partial K|_M$ denotes the perimeter of K measured with respect to a metric M evaluated at the element's centre. Continuous functions $f : [0, \infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and $g : [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ are defined by

$$f(x) = (g(x)(2 - g(x)))^3, \quad g(x) = \min \left(x, \frac{1}{x} \right) = \begin{cases} x, & x \leq 1 \\ \frac{1}{x} & x > 1 \end{cases}. \quad (5.15)$$

The first term (I) is used to control the shape of the element. If K is an equilateral triangle of side length l then basic trigonometry tells us $|K| = l^2 \frac{\sqrt{3}}{4}$ and $|\partial K| = 3l$, whence (I) is unity; otherwise, it is sub-unity. Further, (II) controls the size of K . Inspection of the formula (5.15) implies g takes the maximal value of unity, at $x = 1$. Further, $f(1) = 1$. Both f and g contain a singularity at this point, but their derivatives may be calculated piecewise on the remaining parts of the domain. In particular,

$$\frac{df}{dx}(x) = \begin{cases} -6g(x)^3(2 - g(x))^2x^2, & x < 1 \\ -6g(x)^3(2 - g(x))^2\frac{1}{x^2} & x > 1 \end{cases}. \quad (5.16)$$

Since this derivative is negative on all points at which it is defined (except the origin and in the infinite limit), we conclude f has a single maximum at unity. Term (II) yields unity when the edge lengths of K sum to 3. As we should hope, this occurs when K is an equilateral triangle and its sides have unit length. Again, (II) is sub-unit otherwise.

Thus, the resulting global quality functional of (5.13) gives preference to elements which are equilaterals with unit edges.

5.3 Metric computation

As discussed above, the metric M dictates the way a mesh is adapted from one timestep to the next. In line with Section 4.1, we aim to adapt where our approximation is *most erroneous*, in some sense. This fits with the idea of adapting where the mesh quality functional (5.14) is worst. As mentioned in Subsection 4.1.1, we are motivated by the *Taylor remainder theorem*. Early studies in adaptivity considered gradient-based metrics for this, for example in [Moshfegh et al., 2000]. However, the gradient of a scalar only provides two parameters for meshing, which can be used to refine in x and y directions, whilst the Hessian provides an extra two parameters which can be used to control orientation. In anisotropic mesh optimisation, we derive the metric from some Hessian of the solution field. In *isotropic* mesh adaptation, on the other hand, no sense of

direction or orientation is incorporated into the adaptive process, only magnitude.

For a desired approximation error $\epsilon_{\mathcal{A}} > 0$, recalling (4.1) (where $\mathbf{v} \in \mathbb{R}^2$ represents desired direction and length), we follow [Pain et al., 2001] in defining our metric M such that an element has unit size if the desired error is attained. In this way, consider

$$M = \frac{\gamma}{\epsilon_{\mathcal{A}}} |H|, \quad (5.17)$$

where $\gamma = 1$ is chosen, as in [Pain et al., 2001]. The length of a vector $\mathbf{v} \in \mathbb{R}^2$ can be calculated with respect to M using (5.10), with M_e replaced by M .

Putting aside for now our SW application, consider a *scalar* field $f : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ (rather than a tuple $\mathbf{q} = (\mathbf{u}, \eta) : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^3$). The corresponding Hessian is given by

$$H = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial^2 f}{\partial x^2} & \frac{\partial^2 f}{\partial x \partial y} \\ \frac{\partial^2 f}{\partial y \partial x} & \frac{\partial^2 f}{\partial y^2} \end{bmatrix} = \nabla^T \nabla f. \quad (5.18)$$

Provided $f \in C^2(\Omega)$, the Hessian is symmetric, meaning the first criterion of the definition of a metric being SPD is satisfied. It remains to ensure positive definiteness.

Since numerical issues can arise in the to the division of a square root performed in (5.7), we modify the metric in order to take account for maximal and minimal tolerated element sizes. Denote these values by h_{\max} and h_{\min} , respectively, and denote by a the maximal tolerated aspect ratio for any element, usually taken as $a = 100$.

In order to modify the metric defined in Section 5.1, we follow [Pain et al., 2001] in altering only the eigenvalues of M , resulting in a new metric, with eigen-decomposition changing from (5.5) to $\tilde{M} = V^T \tilde{\Lambda} V$. To obtain the new eigenvalue matrix $\tilde{\Lambda}$, set

$$\tilde{\lambda}_j = \max \left\{ \lambda'_j, \frac{\max\{\lambda'_1, \lambda'_2\}}{a^2} \right\}, \quad \text{where} \quad \lambda'_j = \min \left\{ \frac{1}{h_{\min}^2}, \max \left\{ |\lambda_j|, \frac{1}{h_{\max}^2} \right\} \right\}, \quad (5.19)$$

in the same notation as in [Pain et al., 2001].

In order to avoid issues relating to round-off error, one common approach is to normalise the Hessian used in constructing the metric above, by the scaling

$$\tilde{H} = \frac{1}{\max\{\|\psi\|_{\mathcal{L}_2(\Omega)}, \psi_{\min}\}} H, \quad (5.20)$$

with respect to the (scalar) solution field variable ψ .

An alternative approach, as given in [Alauzet and Loseille, 2016], is to control the interpolation error using the \mathcal{L}_p norm defined on the associated function space. In this approach, the problem of mesh optimisation may be restated (paraphrased from [Alauzet and Loseille, 2016], pp.19) as finding an optimal mesh \mathcal{H}_{opt} of Ω such that the \mathcal{L}_p norm interpolation error is given by

$$\epsilon_{\mathcal{I}}(\mathcal{H}_{opt}) = \min_{\mathcal{H}} \|\mathbf{q} - \Pi_h \mathbf{q}\|_{\mathcal{L}_p(\Omega)}, \quad (5.21)$$

where the minimum is taken over all meshes on Ω and $\Pi_h \cdot$ denotes the interpolation operator. Thus, we seek a target value for the interpolation error as in (4.1), but according to the \mathcal{L}_p norm definition of (5.21).

It is useful to be able to generate a mesh with some target number of elements. Predicting the number of elements for a metric field $\mathcal{M}(\Omega)$ is important so that the computational load of the adaptivity and FEM solver processes can be predicted, too. In this way, if the mesh adaptive procedure is looking as though it will produce a burdensome number of elements for a particular metric, it would be advisable to rescale in order to reduce this. As outlined in [Power et al., 2006], since the domain has a fixed area, the number of elements in the mesh can be calculated using the formula

$$\theta N_{new} = \frac{1}{\gamma} \sum_{K=1}^{N_{old}} |K|, \quad (5.22)$$

where N_{old} and N_{new} denote the numbers of elements before and after adaption and γ and θ are parameters. γ is typically taken to be the area of an ideal element, in this case $\gamma = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}$. It is common practice, as first mentioned in [Pain et al., 2001], to choose the parameter value $\theta = 0.85$, which acknowledges (5.22) is not an exact equality. We scale the (Riemannian) metric $\mathcal{M} = \{M_{\mathbf{x}}\}_{\mathbf{x} \in \Omega}$ determined earlier by a scalar β , determined by

$$\theta N_{new} = \frac{1}{\gamma} \sum_{K=1}^{N_{old}} |K| \sqrt{\det(\beta \mathcal{M}_K)} \iff \beta = \frac{\gamma \theta N_{new}}{\sum_{K=1}^{N_{old}} |K| \sqrt{\det(\mathcal{M}_K)}}, \quad (5.23)$$

where M_K denotes \mathcal{M} evaluated at the barycentre of K .

5.4 Hessian recovery

The Taylor-Hood mixed formulation considered for SW has the free surface displacement as piecewise linear. Thus, the gradient is piecewise constant and the Hessian (5.18) is zero on the interior of each cell and it does not make sense to evaluate the Hessian directly in Firedrake. Instead, we must consider an approach of *Hessian reconstruction*.

There are a number of approaches to recovering the Hessian for a piecewise linear function space, including *integration by parts*, \mathcal{L}_2 *projection* and *quadratic fitting*. These approaches are described and analysed in [Vallet et al., 2007]. In the Hessian recovery problem, we have a (scalar) piecewise linear interpolant $f_{\mathcal{I}} : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ defined on some mesh \mathcal{H} of the domain, with expansion $f_{\mathcal{I}} = \sum_{i=1}^N f_i \phi_i$ over basis functions $\{\phi_i\}_{i=1}^N$ and coefficients $\{f_i\}_{i=1}^N$. Here we approximate what is in reality a smooth function $f : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, such as free surface displacement, over the low-order, piecewise linear space by $f_{\mathcal{I}} = \Pi_h f$ and seek to recover the Hessian $H = \nabla \nabla^T f$ from $f_{\mathcal{I}}$, as defined in (5.18).

The most straightforward approach to Hessian recovery is to implement integration by parts. Thus, we seek to solve (5.18) using FEM, as a sub-problem of the main FEM

problem. For this, we borrow from the approach of [Lakkis and Pryer, 2013] to solving the *Monge-Ampère equation*. Since $H : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{2 \times 2}$, we have a *tensor* FEM problem.² For an appropriate tensor function space T , testing and integrating by parts gives

$$\begin{aligned} \langle H, \tau \rangle_\Omega - \langle \nabla^T \nabla f, \tau \rangle_\Omega &= 0, \quad \forall \tau \in T \\ \iff \langle H, \tau \rangle_\Omega + \langle \nabla f, \nabla \cdot \tau \rangle_\Omega - \int_{\partial\Omega} \begin{bmatrix} f_x \tau_{11} + f_y \tau_{21} \\ f_x \tau_{12} + f_y \tau_{22} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} n_1 \\ n_2 \end{bmatrix} ds &= 0, \quad \forall \tau \in T. \end{aligned} \quad (5.24)$$

In general, we do not have any Neumann boundary conditions to enforce for this integration and so there are no further cancellations of terms to be made.

In our case, of course, the SWE solution tuple (\mathbf{u}, η) is a vector (rather than scalar) solution field. In our tsunami application, the free surface may be argued to be the most important scalar dependent variable, due to the associated issues of gross inundation due to large magnitude waves, although fluid speed provides another suitable candidate.

In the case of *double \mathcal{L}_2 projection*, (5.18) is instead solved using a mixed formulation

$$H = \nabla^T g, \quad g = \nabla f. \quad (5.25)$$

Consider now also a vector function space V , where the gradient $g \in V$. As above, using some vector calculus, we arrive at the following weak form equation pair.

$$\langle H, \tau \rangle_\Omega + \langle g, \nabla \cdot \tau \rangle_\Omega - \int_{\partial\Omega} \begin{bmatrix} g_1 \tau_{11} + g_2 \tau_{21} \\ g_1 \tau_{12} + g_2 \tau_{22} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} n_1 \\ n_2 \end{bmatrix} ds = 0, \quad \forall \tau \in T, \quad (5.26)$$

$$\langle g, \psi \rangle_\Omega - \langle \nabla f, \psi \rangle_\Omega = 0, \quad \forall \psi \in V, \quad (5.27)$$

where $g = (g_1, g_2) = (f_x, f_y)$.

The idea of the *quadratic fitting* method takes a slightly different approach, where f itself is approximated as piecewise quadratic, rather than its derivatives being reconstructed. In the analysis of [Vallet et al., 2007], the \mathcal{L}_2 approach comes out as the most effective, but with integration by parts being cheapest to compute.

5.5 Adapting to multiple solution fields

In some cases, it is beneficial to adapt to *more than one* solution field. The metric operation which allows for us to do this is called *metric intersection*. This operation reduces a finite collection of metrics to a single one. Consider two local metrics, $M_1, M_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{2 \times 2}$. Since

²The following procedure uses the FEM solution provided by Colin Cotter's Firedrake tutorial, found at <http://firedrakeproject.org/demos/ma-demo.py.html#lakkis2013finite>.

$M_1 \succ 0$, we know $M_1^{-\frac{1}{2}}$ exists and is determined by the eigen-decomposition of M_1 ,

$$M_1 = V \begin{bmatrix} \lambda_1 & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda_2 \end{bmatrix} V^T \implies M_1^{-\frac{1}{2}} = V \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{\sqrt{\lambda_1}} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{\sqrt{\lambda_2}} \end{bmatrix} V^T. \quad (5.28)$$

As illustrated in Figure 5.1, the transformation provided by $M^{-\frac{1}{2}}$ represents the mapping taking us from the metric space (\mathbb{R}^2, M_1) to Euclidean space \mathbb{E}^2 . As such, define

$$\widehat{M}_1 = (M_1^{-\frac{1}{2}})^T M_1 M_1^{-\frac{1}{2}} = I_2, \quad \widehat{M}_2 = (M_1^{-\frac{1}{2}})^T M_2 M_1^{-\frac{1}{2}}, \quad (5.29)$$

with eigen-decompositions $\widehat{M}_2 = U \text{diag}(\tilde{\lambda}_1, \tilde{\lambda}_2) U^T$ and $\widehat{M}_1 = U I_2 U^T$ (by construction). As described in [Barral, 2015], the operation of metric intersection first corresponds to modifying the eigenvalues to obtain the new metric and then conjugating by $M_1^{\frac{1}{2}}$:

$$\widehat{M}_{1 \cap 2} = U \begin{bmatrix} \max\{\tilde{\lambda}_1, 1\} & 0 \\ 0 & \max\{\tilde{\lambda}_2, 1\} \end{bmatrix} U^T, \quad M_{1 \cap 2} = (M_1^{\frac{1}{2}})^T \widehat{M}_{1 \cap 2} M_1^{\frac{1}{2}}. \quad (5.30)$$

As is noted in [Barral, 2015], intersection of metrics is non-commutative. That is, $M_{1 \cap 2} \neq M_{2 \cap 1}$. As such, we should be careful in choosing the order of metric intersection, and note mesh optimality is no longer guaranteed. Non-commutativity can be understood most simply in the geometric interpretation of metrics as ellipses: the intersection $M_{1 \cap 2}$ *cannot* be represented by the geometric intersection of the ellipses representing M_1 and M_2 , since the resulting shape is not in general elliptic; instead, it is interpreted as the largest ellipse contained within this geometric intersection.

Let $\{M_i\}_{i=1}^n$ be a finite set of metrics. Given the intersection procedure $M_{1 \cap 2} = \mathcal{I}(M_1, M_2)$, intersection over several fields is trivial:

$$M_{\cap_{i=1}^n M_i} = \mathcal{I}(\dots \mathcal{I}(\mathcal{I}(M_1, M_2), M_3), \dots). \quad (5.31)$$

Choosing the order of intersection is the more difficult part.

5.6 Metric gradation

In some cases, mesh adaptivity can produce meshes which are extremely coarse in some regions of the domain, potentially leading to a mass accumulation of errors. When considering complex boundary geometries, extreme coarsity near boundaries can yield ‘*needling*’ behaviour, where long, thin elements protrude into the domain. This occurs because PRAgMaTIC cannot remove boundary edges or vertices (i.e. alter domain geometry), so the number of DOFs on the boundary is much larger than the metric might dictate. In order to remedy this, we take the approach described in [Alauzet, 2010], as follows.

Consider an edge $\mathbf{pq} \in \mathcal{H}$ of the current mesh. Due to (5.9), \mathbf{pq} has lengths

$$\ell_{\mathbf{p}} = \sqrt{\mathbf{pq}^T M_{\mathbf{p}} \mathbf{pq}}, \quad \ell_{\mathbf{q}} = \sqrt{\mathbf{pq}^T M_{\mathbf{q}} \mathbf{pq}}, \quad (5.32)$$

as evaluated in each endpoint metric. In the isotropic case, $\ell_{\mathbf{p}} = \frac{\|\mathbf{pq}\|_2}{h_{\mathbf{p}}}$ and $\ell_{\mathbf{q}} = \frac{\|\mathbf{pq}\|_2}{h_{\mathbf{q}}}$, by (5.12). Let $h_{\mathbf{p}}$ and $h_{\mathbf{q}}$ denote $h_{\mathcal{M}}$ evaluated at \mathbf{p} and \mathbf{q} , respectively. Consequently the length ratio $a := \frac{\ell_{\mathbf{p}}}{\ell_{\mathbf{q}}}$ also gives a ratio $a = \frac{h_{\mathbf{q}}}{h_{\mathbf{p}}}$ between element sizes. Using (5.9), linear interpolation along edge \mathbf{pq} provides a convex parametrisation

$$h(t) = (1-t)h_{\mathbf{p}} + th_{\mathbf{q}}, \quad t \in [0, 1], \quad \text{whence} \quad \ell_{\mathcal{M}}(\mathbf{pq}) = \ell_{\mathbf{p}} \frac{\log(a)}{a-1}. \quad (5.33)$$

In the *isotropic* case, consider a Riemannian metric $\mathcal{M} = \{\text{diag}(h_{\mathbf{x}}^{-2}, h_{\mathbf{x}}^{-2})\}_{\mathbf{x} \in \Omega}$. As in [Alauzet, 2010], the *size gradation* of edge \mathbf{pq} is defined by

$$c(\mathbf{pq}) = \max \left\{ \frac{h_{\mathbf{p}}}{h_{\mathbf{q}}}, \frac{h_{\mathbf{q}}}{h_{\mathbf{p}}} \right\}^{\ell_{\mathcal{M}}(\mathbf{pq})^{-1}} \geq 1, \quad (5.34)$$

which describes the way in which size requirements on h vary over the domain. The aim of metric gradation is to impose a *gradation parameter* β such that h only grows by this much over a distance $\ell_{\mathcal{M}}$, thus ensuring that adjacent elements do not have a great disparity in their respective sizes. To this end, we scale h by $\beta^{\ell_{\mathcal{M}}}$, which means \mathcal{M} is reduced to a new metric $\widetilde{\mathcal{M}}$ wherever $c(\mathbf{pq}) > \beta$, whereby $c(\mathbf{pq}) = \beta$ is enforced. Typically, $\beta = 1.4$ is chosen in practice and is the value considered in this work.

Continuing as in [Alauzet, 2010], assume $h_{\mathbf{p}} \leq h_{\mathbf{q}}$ (without loss of generality) and denote element sizes on the reduced metric by $\widetilde{h}_{\mathbf{x}}$, for $\mathbf{x} \in \Omega$. We substitute $r = \frac{\widetilde{h}_{\mathbf{q}}}{h_{\mathbf{p}}}$ into (5.34) and interpolate linearly on h by (5.33). Thus, insisting $c(\mathbf{pq}) = \beta$ requires reduction of the metric at vertex \mathbf{q} using

$$\widetilde{M}_{\mathbf{q}(\mathbf{p})} = \text{diag}(\widetilde{h}_{\mathbf{q}}^{-2}, \widetilde{h}_{\mathbf{q}}^{-2}) = (1 + \ell_{\mathbf{p}}(\mathbf{pq}) \ln(\beta))^{-2} M_{\mathbf{p}}, \quad \text{i.e.} \quad \widetilde{M}_{\mathbf{q}(\mathbf{p})} = \eta^2(\mathbf{pq}) M_{\mathbf{p}}. \quad (5.35)$$

Here η provides a scale factor, dependent on the two vertices $\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q} \in \mathcal{H}$ and on the gradation parameter β , which dictates how much the metric $M_{\mathbf{p}}$ at one vertex should be ‘grown’ to form the reduced metric $\widetilde{M}_{\mathbf{q}(\mathbf{p})}$ at the other vertex.

In the anisotropic case, length cannot be calculated as simply. For any $\mathbf{x} \in \Omega$,

$$\eta^2(\mathbf{px}) = \left(1 + \sqrt{\mathbf{px}^T M_{\mathbf{p}} \mathbf{px}} \ln(\beta) \right)^{-2}, \quad \text{i.e.} \quad \widetilde{M}_{\mathbf{x}(\mathbf{p})} = \eta^2(\mathbf{px}) M_{\mathbf{p}}. \quad (5.36)$$

Corresponding to each $\mathbf{p} \in \mathcal{H}$, we have a reduced space $\widetilde{\mathcal{M}}_{\mathbf{p}} = \{\widetilde{M}_{\mathbf{x}(\mathbf{p})}\}_{\mathbf{x} \in \Omega}$ spanned by the pointwise metrics, using the scaling (5.36). As explained in [Alauzet, 2010], the spaces $\widetilde{\mathcal{M}}_{\mathbf{p}}$ grow in line with the scale factor η across the domain in such a way that the anisotropy ratio is preserved, with linear growth in each magnitude. Using these spaces,

we define the reduced Riemannian space using metric intersection defined in Section 5.5,

$$\widetilde{\mathcal{M}} = \left\{ \left(\bigcap_{\mathbf{p} \in \mathcal{H}} \widetilde{\mathcal{M}}_{\mathbf{p}}(\mathbf{x}) \right) \cap \widetilde{\mathcal{M}}(\mathbf{x}) \right\}_{\mathbf{x} \in \Omega}. \quad (5.37)$$

As such, we enforce the strongest constraint on element size across metrics in (5.37).

Using linear interpolation of the metric, we need only compute (5.37) at each vertex. However, [Alauzet, 2010] states that the associated algorithm is of quadratic complexity, so is computationally cumbersome. Instead, we follow the approach of only evaluating intersections over individual edges. For an edge $\mathbf{pq} \in \mathcal{H}$, we make the approximation

$$\widetilde{\mathcal{M}}(\mathbf{p}) \approx \mathcal{M}(\mathbf{p}) \cap M_{\mathbf{q}}(\mathbf{p}), \quad \widetilde{\mathcal{M}}(\mathbf{q}) \approx \mathcal{M}(\mathbf{q}) \cap M_{\mathbf{p}}(\mathbf{q}). \quad (5.38)$$

5.7 Notes on the adaptive algorithm code

Anisotropic mesh adaptivity functions used in this project are not currently implemented on the master branch of Firedrake. For this reason, we use a different branch³, which will soon be merged into the master. As discussed in Section 4.1, there are three central parts of the adaptive procedure: error estimation, mesh adaption and interpolation. In the following we briefly elaborate on the code required for each of these steps.

As discussed in Section 5.3, for computational purposes, error estimation amounts to computing the Hessian of a scalar field. This is achieved by the function `construct_hessian`. The two main modes of Hessian recovery described in Section 5.4 are both implemented in this function, with selection between them available. Having computed a Hessian, the corresponding metric is computed using `compute_steady_metric`, making modifications described in Section 5.3. Control of the minimal and maximal element sizes tolerated, as well as the maximal aspect ratio a , is allowed. By allowing larger values of a , we may increase mesh anisotropy. Intersection of metrics by (5.30) is achieved by `metric_intersection`. Functions described here are found in the utility script `adaptivity.py`

The crucial adaptivity construct used in this code is the `AnisotropicAdaptation` class. Members thereof take as input a mesh and a metric and have two important functions: `adapted_mesh` and `transfer_solution`. The former holds the adapted mesh, under the metric supplied, whilst the latter interpolates fields from the old mesh to the new mesh. As such, the mesh adaption process is encapsulated in `adapted_mesh`.

Interpolation using `transfer_function` is only currently supported for Lagrange spaces, and not mixed spaces. Since we consider a mixed Taylor-Hood problem, our purposes require a modification. This is provided in the script `interp.py`, as the function `interp_Taylor_Hood`. As well as extending to the mixed case, this function involves a procedure accounting for when a metric dictates a node is moved outside the domain. An implementation of metric gradation is provided by the function `metric_gradation`.

³Found at <https://github.com/taupalosaurus/firedrake/>

5.8 Adaptivity code tests

Before considering time-dependent PDE problems, which require several remeshing steps over the solution process, we test the adaptive algorithm for some steady problems. The following surfaces considered were introduced in [Olivier, 2011]:

$$u_1(x, y) = x^2 + y^2, \quad u_2(x, y) = \tan^{-1}\left(\frac{0.1}{\sin(5y) - 2x}\right) + \tan^{-1}\left(\frac{0.5}{\sin(3y) - 7x}\right). \quad (5.39)$$

Using `sensor_tests.py`, we are able to generate meshes adapted to (5.39), as displayed in Figure 5.2. In each case double \mathcal{L}_2 projection is used for Hessian reconstruction. The algorithm appears to adapt well to the given sensor functions, with the first example yielding a near uniform mesh in the domain interior, as expected due to $\nabla\nabla^T u_1 = \text{diag}(2, 2)$ being constant, although there are some issues on the boundaries.

Let us now consider some temporally varying PDE problems. A simple such problem to consider is the advection and diffusion of a pollutant concentration ϕ , say, under the influence of a constant wind field, $\mathbf{u} = (1, 0) \text{ m s}^{-1}$. Considering a diffusion term with a non-negligible, but still relatively small diffusivity parameter $\nu > 0$, helps to smooth out any small scale spurious structures in the problem. *Burgers' equation* is given by

$$\frac{\partial\phi}{\partial t} + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla\phi - \nu\nabla^2\phi = 0. \quad (5.40)$$

Figure 5.2: Test sensor functions (5.39) and their associated adapted meshes. The initial mesh was uniform with 200 vertices in each direction. Maximal element size and anisotropy were set as $h_{\max} = 0.1$ and $a_{\max} = 10^3$, with minimal element size as given.

Consider a rectangular domain $\Omega = [0, 4] \times [0, 1] \text{ m}^2$ and a Gaussian initial condition

$$\phi(x, y) = 0.001 \exp(-25((x - \alpha)^2 + (y - \beta)^2)), \quad (5.41)$$

with $\alpha = \beta = 0.5$. Code for this test case is provided by `Burgers_test.py`.

Choosing $h_{\min} = 5 \text{ mm}$ and $h_{\max} = 100 \text{ mm}$ as defaults, the algorithm adapts the mesh in such a way that the vast majority of the resolution is focused around the bubble of high concentration, as it is advected along the wind direction, as illustrated in Figure 5.3 and in accordance with expectations. In this experiment we take the diffusivity parameter $\nu = 10^{-3} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and perform Hessian reconstruction by double \mathcal{L}_2 projection.

In the above, adaption is performed with respect to a single scalar dependent variable, ϕ , of a scalar PDE (5.40). Incorporating adaptivity into the SWEs is a little more difficult, as these comprise a “2+1” pair of coupled PDEs as in (3.1), with vector and scalar dependent variables.⁴

For the next test problem, we take a step towards the realistic tsunami case by considering a SW problem with a shelf break discontinuity, as in Section 4.4. Consider the extension of our rectangular domain to a square domain $\Omega = [0, 4] \times [0, 4] \text{ m}^2$, with a shelf break from 1 cm depth down to 10 cm depth, occurring 50 cm from the left-hand boundary and with the same initial condition as in (5.41), but now with $\alpha = \beta = 2$, so that the Gaussian bell is centred within the domain. The script file of `simple_adaptive_SW.py` adaptively solves the linear SWEs (3.2) for this setup. As is illustrated in Figure 5.4,

⁴The SWEs can also be interpreted as a system of three PDEs with three scalar dependent variables or, in the linear case, as a single vector PDE (3.3).

Figure 5.3: Advection and diffusion of the initial concentration (5.41) for $\alpha = \beta = 0.5$, according to Burger’s equation (5.40), with wind field $\mathbf{u} = (1, 0)$, purely in the x -direction.

Figure 5.4: Linear SW simulation for initial condition (5.41) with $\alpha = \beta = 2$ and a shelf break discontinuity.

the mesh resolution successfully ‘follows’ the rings propagating outwards from the initial spreading of the initial condition. As we saw in considering the adjoint problem, increased mesh resolution in the latter subplot indicates that the most significant region of the domain for this simulation is the part in the shallow water area ‘near to the shore’.

In the SW test case considered here, we adapt only to the fluid speed, not the free surface displacement, or individual components of the fluid velocity. Using the theory as discussed in Section 5.5, and `metric_intersection`, we can adapt to these fields, too.

There is, however, an issue with the meshes generated in Figure 5.4. Examining them more closely, it becomes apparent that the denser patches of mesh resolution are often ‘lagging behind’ the crest of the wave itself. This occurs mainly because the mesh is not adapted at every timestep and, when it is, is adapted based on a Hessian reconstructed from the *current* timestep. In this way, the regions flagged as requiring finer mesh resolution do not necessarily have this requirement for the coming timesteps until the next mesh regeneration. In order to combat this issue, we next consider *goal-based adaptivity*.

5.9 Goal-based mesh adaptivity

Thus far, adaption has been based on a metric calculated from solution data at the *current timestep*. *Goal-based mesh adaptivity* seeks to improve this metric, incorporating approximations to the dynamics within regions of the solution field which greatly affect those in the spatial (and temporal) region of interest. For the linear SW case, this involves evaluating an objective functional (3.13) and using the numerical solution of the adjoint equations (3.18). Although the method can be applied more generally, we restrict attention to the linear SW case henceforth, for simplicity. For objective functional (3.13),

$$f(\mathbf{x}, t) = \mathbb{1}_A(\mathbf{x}) \eta(\mathbf{x}, t) \quad \implies \quad \frac{\partial f}{\partial \mathbf{u}} = \mathbf{0}, \quad \frac{\partial f}{\partial \eta} = \mathbb{1}_A(\mathbf{x}), \quad (5.42)$$

where A we have made the (reasonable) assumption that the near-coastal region of importance A is contained within the solution image Ω_s . In this way, the adjoint equations (3.18) have a constant source term in the region A .

Given our numerical solution tuple for the SWEs (3.2), we first estimate the error made in the consequent computation of the functional J , providing a measure of what is deemed to be *important*. In this way, the error estimation stage has the purpose of flagging certain areas of the mesh for refinement, coarsening or movement.

To quote pp.1 of [Rannacher, 2009], goal-based adaptivity “means the optimization of the mesh and possibly also the discrete model itself on the basis of an a posteriori error estimate”. Such an error estimate takes the general form

$$J(\mathbf{q}) - J(\mathbf{q}_h) \approx e(\mathbf{q}_h) = \sum_{K \in \mathcal{H}} e_K(\mathbf{q}_h), \quad (5.43)$$

where \mathbf{q}_h denotes our FEM approximation to the (exact) solution tuple \mathbf{q} on a mesh \mathcal{H} , with *local cell-oriented error indicators* e_K summing to give a global error indicator e . Having made an effective choice of error estimator, we seek to minimise the error $|J(\mathbf{q}) - J(\mathbf{q}_h)|$ as in (5.43). To specify the quality of our solution to this problem, we set an upper bound on the error estimate for acceptance.

Given an approximation to the solution of the adjoint equations, we make a similar, vectorised version of the argument found in [Power et al., 2006] (to account for the fact we have not just one solution field, but three). In the *steady* case (where time derivative terms are neglected) we obtain the approximation

$$J(\mathbf{q}) - J(\mathbf{q}_h) \approx \langle \mathcal{R}(\mathbf{q}_h), \boldsymbol{\lambda}_h \rangle_{\Omega_s}, \quad (5.44)$$

which involves both the residual of the forward problem and the approximation to the adjoint problem solution. Thus, in this approach, (5.44) enables us to estimate the associated error in our approximation to the objective functional. There are many other possible choices of error estimate, two of which we discuss in the following. The integral right hand side of (5.44) is approximated using quadrature, in the form of (5.43).

We know the exact solution satisfies $\mathcal{R}(\mathbf{q}) = \mathbf{0}$. For some linear operator \mathcal{L} and what amounts to a source term \mathbf{s} , decomposing by $\mathcal{R}(\mathbf{q}_h) = \mathcal{L}\mathbf{q}_h - \mathbf{s}$, substituting in (5.44) and applying *Green’s theorem* (ignoring surface terms, as recommended in [Power et al., 2006]) gives an alternative error estimate

$$J(\mathbf{q}) - J(\mathbf{q}_h) \approx \langle \mathbf{q} - \mathbf{q}_h, \mathcal{L}^* \boldsymbol{\lambda}_h \rangle_{\Omega_s}. \quad (5.45)$$

For a more accurate error estimate, other approaches are available. Some approaches consider the *discrete form* of the adjoint, as opposed to the continuous one used above. Another method, described in [Power et al., 2006], is to make ‘*coarse-grid*’ approximations to the residual. This involves solving the PDE on different mesh resolutions, in order to

gain some information concerning how much the residual $\mathcal{R}(\mathbf{q}_h)$ strays from zero.

The SWEs (3.2) considered form an unsteady PDE, so it is not so straightforward as to apply steady error estimates at each timestep. An approach to unsteady goal-based anisotropic mesh adaptivity is described in [Belme et al., 2012], which details the extensions required for inner products. For simplicity, however, we follow the approach of [Davis and LeVeque, 2016] and consider the simplified error estimate for (5.44),

$$J(\mathbf{q}) - J(\mathbf{q}_h) \approx \langle \mathbf{q}_h, \boldsymbol{\lambda}_h \rangle_{\Omega_s}. \quad (5.46)$$

The estimate in (5.46) is calculated using *vertex-oriented* error indicators

$$e_{\mathbf{p}}(\mathbf{q}_h; t) = \max_{\tau \in [\tilde{t}, t]} |\mathbf{q}_h(\mathbf{p}, t)^T \boldsymbol{\lambda}_h(\mathbf{p}, \tau)|, \quad \text{where } \tilde{t} = \max\{t - T_{\text{end}} + T_{\text{start}}, 0\}. \quad (5.47)$$

In this approach, at time t , we consider the inner product of forward and adjoint solution approximations over a time range $[\tilde{t}, t]$ within which the objective (3.13) is non-zero.

In the isotropic case, the discretised metric field $\mathcal{M} = \{M_{\mathbf{p}}\}_{\mathbf{p} \in \mathcal{H}}$ is simply defined by $M_{\mathbf{p}} = \text{diag}(e_{\mathbf{p}}(\mathbf{q}_h; t)^{-2}, e_{\mathbf{p}}(\mathbf{q}_h; t)^{-2})$. To construct the metric in the anisotropic case, on the other hand, we begin by adapting to a field related to the fluid flow, such as free surface displacement, as usual. We then scale the metric at each vertex by the error indicator. This may be interpreted as replacing the error requirement ϵ of (5.17) with

$$\tilde{\epsilon} = \frac{\epsilon}{e_{\mathbf{p}}(\mathbf{q}_h; t)} \quad (5.48)$$

Through (5.48), we insist that the error is smaller, and hence that *the solution is of better quality* in the ‘significant’ regions flagged by the error indicator. In regions of less significance, $\tilde{\epsilon}$ takes larger values, meaning that a coarser mesh is allowed.

The general goal-based mesh adaptive procedure is summarised by Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1: Goal-based mesh adaptive process

```

/* Fixed mesh adjoint run                                     */
Solve the adjoint problem (backwards in time, from  $t = T$ ) on a constant, coarse
mesh and save the solution data.;
/* Adaptive mesh forward run                                 */
for each timestep  $t^n$  (forward in time, from  $t = 0$ ) do
    Estimate the error at  $t^n$ , using an error estimate (5.43) and the saved data.;
    Feed the error estimate into the adaptive algorithm by replacing the  $\epsilon$  of (5.17)
    by the updated error requirement (5.48).;
    Regenerate the mesh, interpolate variables and solve the forward problem.;
end

```

6. Tsunami application

As discussed in Chapter 2, this project aims to simulate the tsunami which struck the coast of Fukushima, Japan, in 2011, both accurately and efficiently, using anisotropic mesh adaptivity. The process by which this was achieved is explained in this chapter, with results, analyses and conclusions provided in Sections 6.4 and 6.5.

6.1 Computational setup for the Tōhoku tsunami

In order to run computations for the example considered, a GIS domain boundary file was constructed using shore-line data from GSHHG, along with bathymetry data from GEBCO. By separating the coastline into parts, we are able to indicate geographical regions where the initial mesh should be finer, such as near to Fukushima. Different GSHHG resolutions are used for the two coastal boundaries near to Fukushima and elsewhere, so small, distant island features are not resolved, otherwise incurring computational expense.

Figure 6.1 illustrates the boundary segments used, with bathymetry data visible in the background. Due to the use of different databases for bathymetry and coastlines, with disagreeing sea-level contours, it is necessary to cap the bathymetry so that it is never shallower than 30m, say.

The domain boundary $\partial\Omega$ comprises of the (disjoint) union of segments $\partial\Omega_O$, $\partial\Omega_F$ and $\partial\Omega_C$, denoting the open ocean boundary, region of interest surrounding Fukushima and remaining coastal boundary, respectively. A simplification has been made along $\partial\Omega_C$, as indicated in Figure 6.1, where a (relatively) small gap between land masses of Hokkaido and Honshu, the *Tsugaru Strait*, has been closed, as if there exists a sea wall. This is justified as it is sufficiently far from both the earthquake epicentre and the region of interest that any effect the discrepancy may have on the final solution will be negligible.

In solving fluids problems on the entire Earth, or when considering timescales of the order of the tides, one should acknowledge both that the Earth is rotating (as manifested in

Figure 6.1: Domain geometry for the Tōhoku tsunami. Boundary segments $\partial\Omega_O$, $\partial\Omega_F$ and $\partial\Omega_C$ are shown in blue, magenta and orange, respectively. White numbers correspond to boundary identity tags. Bathymetry is shown using the QGIS Google Maps plugin.

the Coriolis force) and the fact the Earth is (almost) a sphere. We have already discussed the former. With respect to the latter, one approach is to re-define the SWEs in spherical polar co-ordinates. However the Earth is not quite a sphere and there are a number of other effective methods which are regularly used in the computational geosciences.

One such approach is transform to *UTM coordinates*, providing not one single map projection, but a series of projections, taken across the whole globe. The UTM approach divides the Earth into 60 *zones*, where each band is 6° in longitude. In addition, zones are divided in the latitudinal direction, given zone letters from the Roman alphabet. UTM coordinates have metric units, taking the horizontal value 500km at zone midpoints. Transformation between latitude-longitude and UTM coordinates is made possible in Python using the functions contained in `conversion.py`¹. Since the domain we consider is contained mainly in zone 54, but also overlaps with zones 53 and 55, we use the `force_zone_number` parameter option in our conversion, set to 54, to avoid discontinuities.

Using the domain geometry generated in QGIS, we can construct meshes using *QMESH online*, recently developed at Imperial College [Avdis et al., 2017]. Each boundary segment of the GIS file is given a ‘PhysID’ physical identification tag, so a different level of meshing can be applied within a gradation distance specified in the meshing process. We distinguish between open ocean (PhysID=100) and coastal boundaries (PhysID=200), as displayed in Figure 6.1 - necessary if we were to enforce Dirichlet boundary conditions.

We also require a means of interpreting the tsunami initial conditions and bathymetry in Firedrake. Initial condition data was provided by the author of [Saito et al., 2011] as `init_profile.xyz`, containing a set of discretised latitudinal and longitudinal coordinates, along with free surface displacement values. This data was processed using GMT to create a NetCDF surface which could be interpolated in Firedrake, along with the bathymetry field. The resulting initial surface profile is displayed in Figure 6.2.

Notice from Figure 6.2 that initial profile of the tsunami is very close to the main Japanese island of Honshu. Witness and measurement reports, such as those used in [Kazama and Noda, 2012], [Okada, 2011] and [Suzuki et al., 2012], mention that the tsunami wave arrived at many Japanese coastal locations within 30 minutes and at some in *just ten minutes*. Since we are mainly interested in modelling the wave’s approach to and reaching of the coast, it is reasonable to assume (and fairly clear from experiments in Figure 6.3 overleaf) that the ocean-bound waves will not reach the open ocean boundary within a 25 minute timeframe. Hence, in our application of the SWEs to this case study, a first approximation is to enforce zero flux over the open ocean boundaries. As discussed in Section 3.3, this approach is not particularly physical when waves interact with

Figure 6.2: Approximation to the initial surface displacement for the Tōhoku tsunami used in this project.

¹These transformation functions can be downloaded from <https://pypi.python.org/pypi/utm>.

the shoreline and approximates what should be open ocean boundaries as impermeable. Nonetheless, it is sufficient for our purposes, as we are most interested in slightly offshore locations, at gauge locations P02 and P06 as displayed in Figure 2.2.

Using code developed in the test problems, an adaptive algorithm for solving the Tōhoku tsunami SW problem is given by `simple_adaptive_tsunami.py`. This script allows for experimentation with different initial QMESH meshes and adaptivity parameters. Adjoint problem solution information is incorporated in `goal-based_tsunami.py`.

6.2 Model verification

After establishing the governing SWEs in Section 3.1, we made the simplification of linearity, as in (3.2). We expect the linearised equations to be computationally cheaper to solve than the nonlinear case, hence preferring to use them in our calculations. Before implementing mesh adaptivity in the Tōhoku tsunami case, let us briefly compare the two approaches to verify the assumption of linearity for ocean-scale SW dynamics.

A first comparison of these approaches can be made using an ‘*eyeball norm*’ consideration

of the solutions provided across the entire domain, at a particular point in time. Henceforth an implicit midpoint method is used, with timesteps of length 1 second. Subfigures 6.3a and 6.3b display the shallow water solutions given by the linear and nonlinear, non-rotational approaches after 25 minutes of simulation time, respectively. It is difficult to distinguish any significant differences in the ocean dynamics at this time level, supporting the claim that using the linear standalone solver might be sufficient. Throughout this section, tests are run on a fixed, fine mesh with 97,343 vertices. In the nonlinear case, we take diffusivity parameter $\nu = 10^{-3}$ and bottom friction coefficient $c_b = 0.0025$.

Additionally, in Section 3.1 the Coriolis effect was assumed to be negligible in tsunami modelling, due to the large difference in timescales and speeds on which the two dynamics act. We can test this assumption numerically by solving the rotational SWEs and comparing the results with the non-rotational case used thus far. As mentioned in Section

Figure 6.3: Free surface displacement approximations in the Tōhoku problem after 25 minutes of simulation time under four SW equation sets, where ‘*rot.*’ denotes ‘*rotational*’.

3.1, in the linear case, the momentum equation corresponding to (3.2) takes the form

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial t} + 2\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{u} + g\nabla\eta = 0. \quad (6.1)$$

Equivalent code for the rotational case of (6.1), along with the nonlinear equations, is provided by `model_verification.py`. Evaluating the free surface displacement after 25 minutes, as illustrated in Subfigures 6.3c and 6.3d, yields results indistinguishable by eye to those obtained in the other, non-rotational cases of Figure 6.3. The Coriolis parameter is evaluated vertex-wise using a transformation back into latitude-longitude coordinates.

The difficulty in making this analysis is that we do not have the true solution of the fluid dynamics which we seek to approximate. For a more rigorous analysis, we consider a time series of free surface values at two particular locations. A disadvantage of this approach is it only gives a localised, pointwise approximation, rather than a global ones given in Figure 6.3. However, if we choose a location corresponding to an ocean gauge, we can compare model approximations against historical data. Two such gauges are the offshore bottom-pressure gauges P02 and P06, illustrated in Figure 2.2. These pressure gauges, operated by Tōhoku University, were active between June 2010 and May 2011.

We use free surface values from P02 and P06 as calculated in the initial surface inversion analysis of [Saito et al., 2011], as illustrated by the blue lines of Subfigures 6.4a and 6.4b. Given the gauge coordinates $(142.5016^\circ, 38.5002^\circ)$ and $(142.5838^\circ, 38.6340^\circ)$, to the nearest tenthousandth of a degree, model outputs may be compared against these data. Using `model_verification.py`, we can run analyses of the various models, yielding the curves in Subfigures 6.4a and 6.4b. The timeseries for the nonlinear solvers are truncated at 25 minutes simulation time, due to extreme computational expense after this point.

It is clear from Figure 6.4 there is very little difference between the model results, for this fixed mesh and for these tide gauges. Making use of Python’s `clock` functionality, we obtain the performance analyses displayed in the table of Subfigure 6.8. Here the averages were taken over two pressure gauge runs considered.²

We observe from Figure 6.8 that the speedup in choosing the linear equations over the nonlinear ones is by a factor of at least 4. In addition, there is a small speedup in considering the linear, non-rotational equations over the linear, rotational equations. It is reasonable to conclude we may exclusively use the linear, non-rotational case henceforth. Our justification is that it provides an similarly accurate and a vastly computationally cheaper approach than the nonlinear cases, and yields a non-negligible saving in computational effort over the linear case wherein the Coriolis effect is considered.

It is also clear from Figure 6.4 that the time series for our solution take the right general shape, mimicking the initial rise and fall in free surface rather well, on this high resolution mesh. However, the latter 35 minutes of simulation time is not approximated so well by our model, using any of the equations considered. This should be expected, because,

²Performance tests were run in series on a MacBook Pro with OS X El Capitan.

Equation set	NL	NN	RL	RN
Mean run time for 25 minutes (s)	1701.4	8338.0	1855.3	8452.85
Mean run time for an hour (s)	3942.1		4335.0	

(c) Timing performance analysis

Figure 6.4: Model simulations for the Tōhoku tsunami, including free surface values calculated in the inversion analysis of [Saito et al., 2011], alongside time performance analysis across the four equation sets, as labelled in Figure 6.3. Data was extracted using *PlotDigitizer*.

as has already been remarked, our choice of boundary condition is rather unrealistic, and produces reflections in the bays around Fukushima which would not occur in reality. Regardless, the poor quality simulation in this time period is of no great concern to us, since we are focused mainly on accurately modelling the tsunami’s approach to the coast.

6.3 Damage quantification

An important aspect of tsunami research, inevitably linked with inundation at the coast, is damage quantification. A common proxy for damage quantification is the base 2 logarithm of the maximal near-coastal free surface displacement, or *tsunami magnitude*,

$$m := \log_2(\eta_{\max}), \quad (6.2)$$

where η_{\max} is calculated across all near-coastal locations of importance. Helpfully, [Lisitzin, 1974] provides a characterisation of the damage caused, as displayed in Subfigure 6.5b.

Due to the boundary conditions used, surface readings taken *on* the coast are likely artificially affected and thus yield significant errors. As such, it makes sense to instead consider the near-coastal locations of GPS wave gauges 801, 802, 803, 804 and 806 depicted in Figure 2.2. Free surface values are interpolated at each gauge and the maximum is taken at each point in time, giving the plot displayed in Subfigure 6.5a. This plot indicates the damage caused by the tsunami was focused at the shore, with some inland damage and loss of life, consistent with reports as discussed in Chapter 2.

Figure 6.5: (a): Damage measures calculated using (6.2), across tide gauges 801, 802, 803, 804 and 806, with damage level thresholds as characterised in the table of (b). (Tabulated data is as displayed on pp.32 of [Pranowo et al., 2010].) (c): The spatial region of importance.

In the goal-based procedure discussed in Section 5.9, we can establish a time-dependent ‘*domain of dependence*’ wherein presence of a tsunami wave could cause inland damage and loss of life. The region of importance A chosen surrounds Daiichi nuclear power plant and shown in Figure 6.5c and envelops gauges P02 and P06, for the purposes of time series analysis in Section 6.4. The derivative of the objective functional (3.13) with respect to the adjoint free surface may be interpreted as a forcing function for the adjoint continuity equation. Choosing an indicator function tends to lead to spurious oscillations in the simulation, resulting from the timestepping method used. Therefore we actually consider a slightly smoothed function, sometimes called a *smooth bump function*,

$$\psi(x, y) = \mathbb{1}_{A \times [T_{\text{start}}, T_{\text{end}}]} \exp\left(\frac{1}{(x-a)^2 - \frac{1}{4}(b-a)^2}\right) \exp\left(\frac{1}{(x-c)^2 - \frac{1}{4}(d-c)^2}\right), \quad (6.3)$$

where $A = [a, b] \times [c, d] = [490 \text{ km}, 640 \text{ km}] \times [4160 \text{ km}, 4360 \text{ km}] \subset \Omega$, $T_{\text{start}} = 5 \text{ mins}$ and $T_{\text{end}} = T = 25 \text{ mins}$. In accordance with observed accounts, we are aware the tsunami will not reach A in the first 5 minutes and do not wish to model the dynamics after 25 minutes of simulation time. The forcing term is only non-zero in this period, as per (3.13).

6.4 Model comparisons

To conclude, we assess the extent to which the adaptive approaches considered provide an effective means of reducing the computational cost of tsunami modelling. In each of the following cases we solve the linear, non-rotational SWEs, as motivated in Section 6.2:

Mesh (i) Constant, coarse mesh with 3,126 vertices;

Mesh (ii) Constant, medium resolution mesh with 17,086 vertices;

Mesh (iii) Constant, fine mesh with 97,343 vertices (as used in Sections 6.2 and 6.3);

Mesh (iv) Simple adaptive mesh simulation, starting with the coarse mesh of (i);

Mesh (v) Goal-based adaptive mesh simulation, starting with the coarse mesh of (i).

We expect coarse mesh run (i) to have lowest computational cost, but to yield the poorest quality solution, since the SW variables are being approximated over piecewise polynomial spaces with relatively few vertices, implying a low DOF count in the Taylor-Hood space. Mesh (ii) is expected to be more expensive, with mesh (iii) considerably more expensive again, in each case using a factor of 5 more vertices than in the previous case. These approaches are expected to provide successively more accurate approximations to the true oceanic dynamics. With meshing approach (iv) we seek to reduce the expense from that of mesh (iii), whilst maintaining a similarly high quality solution. One means of monitoring computational cost is to compare mean vertex counts. Additional computational cost arises in the mesh adaption and interpolation procedures and so we also monitor the run time of each approach to get a broader picture of algorithmic performance. For the final meshing approach (v), we hope the additional information provided by the adjoint equation solution will enable us to obtain a high quality approximation using even fewer vertices, and hence more efficiently, than in the case of (iv).

The resulting plots are displayed in Figure 6.6. For anisotropic mesh adaptivity, the mesh is adapted every 30 timesteps, which are each one second in length, to the intersected Hessian of free surface displacement and fluid speed, using a double \mathcal{L}_2 projection. By selecting the `error` parameter in `plot_gauges`, we may compare error norms between the timeseries resulting from the various meshing approaches and the gauge inversion data,

(a) Model P02 values

(b) Model P06 values

	Norm type	Coarse	Medium	Fine	Simple adaptive	Goal-based
P02	\mathcal{L}_1 norm	0.398	0.291	0.321	0.315	0.255
	\mathcal{L}_2 norm	0.480	0.331	0.355	0.351	0.326
	\mathcal{L}_∞ norm	1.190	0.788	0.780	0.659	1.035
P06	\mathcal{L}_1 norm	0.324	0.128	0.111	0.163	0.106
	\mathcal{L}_2 norm	0.460	0.172	0.136	0.225	0.152
	\mathcal{L}_∞ norm	1.368	0.547	0.390	0.785	0.680

(c) Error norms

Figure 6.6: A time series comparison of different meshing approaches at pressure gauges off the coast of Japan, alongside error norm values for five approaches to meshing in tsunami modelling.

for the 25 minute time period considered. These values are displayed in Subfigure 6.6c. From Subfigures 6.6a and 6.6b, we obtain a sensitivity analysis, which gives support to the claim that the time series resulting from the standalone SW solver converge to reality as the mesh is refined. In particular, for the P06 case, the improvement made on mesh (i) by mesh (ii) in all three norms is considerable, but the subsequent improvement to mesh (iii) is much smaller, despite the additional vertex count increase by a factor of 5. Interestingly, in the P02 case, a better approximation is attained by the medium resolution mesh than the fine mesh in both \mathcal{L}_1 and \mathcal{L}_2 norms. Given more time to investigate these data, this would certainly be something to consider.

Subfigure 6.7b illustrates the mesh generated using the standard anisotropic mesh adaptive algorithm after 14 minutes of simulation time. As we should hope, the mesh resolution is finest in the regions of ocean where free surface displacement and fluid speed are greatest. There is fine mesh resolution in the direction of the coast, where we are interested in the dynamics. However this is also the case in the opposite direction, where a wave is bound for the open ocean. Additionally, there is dense mesh resolution along a long stretch of the Japanese coast, which isn't necessary if we are only interested in the locality of Fukushima.

The first table of Figure 6.8 displays averaged times to completion of SW simulation, for three, increasingly fine, (fixed) mesh resolutions. In addition, the second table of Figure 6.8 displays corresponding data for the two adaptive approaches considered. Timing analyses were made using Python's `clock` functionality, with the average taken twice over each of the runs for the two pressure gauge options, P02 and P06. Note that these calculations involve the calling of Firedrake's `.at` function at every timestep, which interpolates the free surface value at the gauge location. This operation can be rather expensive and so adds additional time to all solvers than would be the case if we only require `.vtu` output.

Despite the heightened run time exhibited, it is clear from Figure 6.6 the 'simple adaptive' mesh approach falls short of making an accurate approximation of the true

Figure 6.7: Meshes generated after 14 minutes of simulation time, with and without guidance by adjoint information, for the Tōhoku tsunami problem.

Fixed mesh type	Coarse mesh (i)	Medium mesh (ii)	Fine mesh (iii)
Mean run time for an hour (s)	82.1	548.3	3942.1
Mean run time for 25 mins (s)	39.9	239.3	1701.4
Vertex count	3,126	17,086	97,343
Hourly run time per vertex (s)	0.026	0.032	0.040

Mesh-adaptive approach	‘Simple adaptive’ (iv)	Goal-based (v)	Gradated (vi)
Mean run time for 25 mins (s)	1602.8	1486.9	2287.4
Minimum vertex count	3126	2894	2109
Maximum vertex count	6437	7194	7194
Mean vertex count	5896	3403	3756

Figure 6.8: Time performance analyses for various meshing approaches to tsunami modelling.

dynamics, particularly at the free surface peak. As well as the explanations offered above, this could be due to a large interpolation error resulting from frequent mesh regenerations.

Finally, a goal-based simulation is performed, solving the adjoint equations on a relatively coarse, fixed mesh with 7,194 vertices. This is done so that features of the adjoint solution are sufficiently resolved so as to provide useful information to feed into the adaptive procedure. Whilst the simulation on this mesh performs excellently in terms of its accuracy (see Figure 6.6), run time and DOF count, as is clear from Figure 6.8.

An issue with the goal-based simulation, however, is that the mesh has undesirably long, thin elements protruding into the domain from the open ocean boundaries. In the cases of some parameter choices, such meshes can lead to massive error accumulations. As such, the metric gradation is something to be considered. The complex boundaries of the Tōhoku problem domain provide a suitable candidate. In addition to the gradation process described in Section 5.6, we intersect the metric with the initial metric (only) on the boundaries. In this way, we enforce the strongest constraint on element size, meaning the mesh is only ever finer than the initial mesh on the boundaries, and never coarser. The corresponding metric-gradated mesh at $t = 14$ mins is displayed in Subfigure 6.7d.

An issue with gradating the metric in the way described above, however, is that computational expense rises, both in terms of DOFs and time, as indicated in Figure 6.8. Nonetheless, the resulting meshing approach still has a lower vertex count than with the medium resolution, fine and ‘simple adaptive’ mesh approaches. Whilst vertex count depends only on the method by which meshes are generated, regardless of the exact computations involved to obtain the results, run time can usually be improved. There are a number of ways in which the adaptivity code can be made more computationally efficient, particularly in the metric gradation step. One of these is to implement metric gradation in C, where iteration loops are computationally cheaper than in Python. In addition, since 2D metrics are symmetric 2×2 matrices, we could save on both storage and operation count by redefining matrix products to only act on the upper triangular part. If sufficient time were available to implement these coding efficiencies, and more, then the metric gradated approach would be more competitive in terms of run time.

6.5 Conclusions and future work

In conclusion to this thesis, *anisotropic mesh adaptivity* provides a means of maintaining both a low vertex count during tsunami modelling and a sufficiently well-resolved region surrounding important parts of the dynamics. To an extent, the application of mesh adaptivity removes the (difficult) problem of generating a high quality mesh of the domain, and can work well using a fairly coarse initial mesh. Each of the adaptive approaches considered were initialised with relatively coarse mesh of at most 7,194 vertices.

In addition, solving the adjoint problem can be useful for guiding the mesh adaptive process, offering additional information not available in the case where only the forward problem is considered. For the Tōhoku tsunami, implementing anisotropic mesh adaptivity alone is not enough to resolve waves accurately, even when the mesh is adapted to both the surface and fluid speed. Nor does this ‘*simple adaptive*’ approach do so in the most efficient manner, inserting many DOFs to resolve features of the fluid dynamics which will never effect coastal inundation, which we seek to monitor. Both the number of vertices and the number of mesh regenerations required in obtaining an accurate solution (in the relevant locations) can be reduced using a ‘*goal-based*’ approach. Figure 6.8 shows this method is able to far out-perform all of the others considered, although in some cases producing meshes with undesirable properties. Such properties can be remedied by implementation of *metric gradation*. Whilst the goal-based approach can result in large errors outside of the region of interest, this can be assumed to be of no great concern.

As have been highlighted throughout this project, there are a number of ways in which our approximation could be improved. Firstly, the ‘*zero flux*’ boundary conditions imposed on our PDE are very unrealistic, both for use with coastal and with open ocean boundaries. A better approach for the coasts would be to implement a *wetting and drying* algorithm specifying the coasts in particular using the tag `PhysID=200`. Further, instead of using the standalone SW solver developed throughout this project, we could make use of the optimised code available in *Thetis*. This unstructured grid ocean modelling framework enables the user to use wetting and drying at coastal boundaries.

A major improvement to the goal-based algorithm would be to estimate errors in the objective functional using the residual inner product (5.44), rather than an \mathcal{L}_2 inner product between primal and adjoint approximations. This could be achieved using *coarse-grid* approximations to the residual, as described in [Power et al., 2006], could lead to a better error estimate and hence improve our simulations further. It would also be beneficial to consider unsteady anisotropic adaptive algorithms, as in [Belme et al., 2012].

As motivated in Section 4.2, it would be highly beneficial to incorporate r-adaptivity into the mesh adaptive tsunami model developed in this thesis. By doing so, DOFs could be allowed to move with features of fluid flow, such as tsunami waves, rather than be removed and injected into the domain at a heightened computational cost. It is this possibility in particular which will form the core of future research.

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